

Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities

D2.3 VITAL-5G experimentation platform & Open Repository – first full version

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
DCM	Data Collection Manager
DSM	Data Storage Manager
EXPB	Experiment Blueprint
EXPD	Experiment Descriptor
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HMI	Human Machine Interface
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JWT	JSON Web Token
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCM	LifeCycle Manager
ML	Machine Learning
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
N/A	Not Applicable
NBI	NorthBound Interface
NFVO	Network Function Virtualisation Orchestrator
OSM	Open Source MANO
QoE	Quality of Experience
RBAC	Role-based Access Control
REST	Representational State Transfer
SBI	SouthBound Interface
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
TCB	TestCase Blueprint
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VSB	Vertical Service Blueprint
VSD	Vertical Service Descriptor
VSI	Vertical Service Instance

Executive Summary

Deliverable D2.3 “VITAL-5G experimentation platform & Open Repository – first full version”, is the third deliverable of WP2 “VITAL-5G Platform Implementation”, and includes the more mature outcomes of T2.1, T2.2, T2.3 and T2.4 in terms of software assets produced for the VITAL-5G platform and the VITAL-5G NetApps supporting the use cases of the project.

The objective of this deliverable is to document and provide the functionalities delivered as part of the first full release of the VITAL-5G platform and the VITAL-5G NetApps. In this sense this document elaborates on the features of the first full-release, their software architecture with a highlight on the software components that are part of this release as well as APIs and interfaces offered by the components/NetApps.

Special attention has been given to describing the updates to baseline software (either from previous/ongoing research projects or internal assets of the partners – if any) that have been undertaken in order to develop VITAL-5G components as well as to the provision of links to the software artifacts to be used as delivery mechanism (e.g., link to opensource code repositories, software packages, etc) of the first full release.

The first full release of the VITAL-5G platform enables support for the missing VITAL-5G platform capabilities such as automated monitoring configuration, monitoring data retrieval and visualization, 5G network slice management capabilities, GUI-based service lifecycle management and AI-based analytics for service troubleshooting.

With 2 exceptions, the first full releases of all the NetApps are available and offer functionalities to support services for all 3 use cases of the project such as: data collection from vessels, ingestion, fusion, processing and organization, navigation-related functionalities and functionalities that enable human-robot collaboration.

Finally, AI/ML functionalities are introduced both in the platform modules (AI-based analytics module) and in the NetApps (VA2 and VA3). These enable advanced features such as automated service analysis, enhanced experiment reports, automated closed-control loops for the 5G network and remote inspection and risk assessment in a vessel.

Overall, the first full release components and NetApps represent a stable version of the VITAL-5G platform setting the stage for the 3rd year of the project and the delivery of the final VITAL-5G solution.

1 Introduction

1.1 Aim and scope of deliverable

VITAL-5G aims to ease T&L service design, management, and experimentation on top of 5G enabled testbeds to both internal partners of the project and 3rd party external experimenters. The key to achieve this is the delivery of a platform built upon the concept of Networked Applications (NetApps), which offers high-level interfaces supporting the T&L service design, lifecycle management, automated optimization and validation and interactions of 5G-enabled infrastructures for the deployment of the services, allocation of the 5G network slices and extraction of the monitoring metrics. Moreover, within VITAL-5G we develop a set of NetApps which aim to showcase T&L uses cases, validate the overall functionality of the platform, and at the same time ease the 3rd party service design and experimentation through the re-usage of existing NetApps.

This document builds mainly upon D2.1 [1] and D2.2 [2], which describe the software architectures and high-level interfaces of the platform modules and NetApps and the first full release features of the platform modules and NetApps. In brief Deliverable D2.3 serves to:

- Document the services and functionalities of the VITAL-5G platform supported in the first full version, by determining the set of modules and sub-modules released in this release, the supported APIs, the delivery mechanism and the license of each module. The focus of this release is enhancing the support, adding the monitoring and experimentation capabilities on top of the service design and lifecycle management supported on the early-drop release.
- Document the VITAL-5G NetApps released with the first full release and the functionality supported. In this sense this document describes the functional blocks of the NetApps, the supported features of each block and the link to the software assets supporting the NetApp logic (and the licenses and constraints for the usage of each NetApp).

This document is intended to be used by external parties to understand the functionalities of the platform and the NetApps produced by the project, and to guide the internal integration activities.

1.2 Mapping VITAL-5G Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map VITAL-5G's Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1 Adherence to VITAL-5G's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
T2.1 NetApps development (Covered by D2.1, D2.2, D2.3, D2.4)	The main goal of this task is the development of the vertical specific and agnostic NetApps, that will be used in the VITAL-5G use cases and the respective relevant features	Section 3	Section 3 provides NetApps which released as part of the first full release of VITAL-5G and therefore will be available on the Open online repository
	The first phase of this task refers to the design and	Section 3	Section 3 covers the design and updates of the NetApps available on

	<p>implementation of NetApps in terms of number of VNFs in a service chain, and placement of VNFs on top of the vertical and cross-vertical infrastructure, based on the use case requirements that are recognized and defined in T1.1.</p>		<p>the first full release of the platform. This is the description in terms of functional blocks, mapping to software assets, contributions of the VITAL-5G project and the targeted scenarios for the deployment of the NetApps (usage of 5G slices, IoT devices, etc).</p>
	<p>In the second phase of the task, the developed NetApps will be available at the Open online NetApp repository to be used by 3rd party experimenters, while the necessary functionality and tools will be developed to allow for the creation, onboarding, and instantiation of additional NetApps by other experimenters</p>	<p>Section 2, Section 3</p>	<p>In Section 2 we describe the interfaces introduced into the VITAL-5G platform for this first full release in order to support the high-level interfaces described in D1.2 [3]. In Section 3 we list and describe the first full release NetApps highlighting potential uses by 3rd party experimenters.</p>
<p>T2.2 VITAL-5G platform enhancement & Open repository development (Covered by D2.1, D2.2, D2.3, D2.4)</p>	<p>The goal of this task is to implement the two main blocks of the VITAL-5G's Open platform, i.e., VITAL-5G portal and Open Online repository</p>	<p>Section 2</p>	<p>In Section 2 we describe the VITAL-5G first full release focusing on the updates to the early drop release and the VITAL-5G contributions to the initial software baseline.</p>
<p>T2.3 NetApp verification tools (Covered by D2.2, D2.3, D2.4)</p>	<p>This task deals with verification and validation tools, methodologies, and benchmarking procedures. The validation tools will be developed and used to pre-validate the NetApps (in the lab) and to fully validate NetApps using the VITAL-5G platform (in the field).</p>	<p>Section 2</p>	<p>Section 2.4 describes the second release of the NetApp validation tool which focuses on the NetApp blueprint syntax and consistency validation, validation of the NetApp IoT device dependencies in the targeted testbed and dynamic KPI monitoring and validation</p>
<p>T2.4 Application & intelligence development (Covered by D2.2, D2.3, D2.4)</p>	<p>The main activities of this task are: i) definition and implementation of intelligent applications for the project use cases, ii) definition and</p>	<p>Section 2, Section 3, Section 4</p>	<p>Sections 2.10 and 2.11 describe the AI-based diagnostics platform module, which uses AI algorithms to determine the cause of service underperformances to: (i) Elaborate detailed experimentation reports;</p>

	<p>implementation of distributed data ingestion, fusion and post-processing techniques for the experimentation data, iii) development of the Intent Based and Diagnostics mechanisms, and iv) (self) optimization of use cases based on intelligence inferred from steps ii) and iii).</p>	<p>(ii) Produce diagnostics events which may trigger service lifecycle management actions to mitigate the problem. Section 4.1 details the workflows used to enable AI-based closed-control loops for network service scaling and network slice modification at the platform level. Section 3 elaborates on VS8 which collects and stores information from the vessel’s Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS), and VA2 and VA3 which supports the ingestion of IoT sensor data from a wide range of IoT devices. These NetApps support interfaces for consuming the historical data which shall enable the data ingestion for AI/ML algorithms.</p>
DELIVERABLE		
<p>D2.3 VITAL-5G experimentation platform & Open Repository – first full version</p> <p>The first full drop of the VITAL-5G experimentation platform including all accompanying tools and functionalities.</p>		

1.3 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The rest of the content of this document is structured as follows:

- Section 2: Details VITAL-5G platform components released in the first full version, together with the description of the supported features and APIs, the delivery mechanisms for each module and the contributions of the project to the baseline software.
- Section 3: Details the list of NetApps available on the first full version, together with the supported functionality and targeted deployment
- Section 4: Builds upon the workflows established in D1.2 [3] adding workflows to support new functionalities or providing implementation specific details to the already established workflows.
- Section 5: Concludes this document outlining the results achieved with this first full release of the VITAL-5G platform and NetApps and the following steps regarding the platform and NetApp development and delivery.

2 VITAL-5G experimentation platform first full version

As described in D2.2 the early-drop release of the VITAL-5G platform focused in supporting the NetApp, Vertical Service catalogue management operations, and in providing initial service and experiment lifecycle management capabilities. In this first-full release version of the platform we enable support for the missing VITAL-5G platform capabilities, namely:

- **Automated monitoring configuration, monitoring data retrieval and visualization:** This release includes the first drop of the VITAL-5G Monitoring platform, integrated with the rest of the modules of the platform for the configuration, ingestion, distribution, and visualization of the metrics associated with the NetApps, Services and Experiments.
- **5G Network Slice Management capabilities:** This release introduces the VITAL-5G Slice Inventory module, which provides the platform 5G slice catalogue and lifecycle management capabilities of the platform, integrated in the service lifecycle management workflows for automated allocation of the 5G slices given the slice profile characteristics of the service and the NetApps.
- **Experiment execution and report generation support:** This release supports the execution of experiments and the visualization of the experiment reports, with the validation of the experiment KPIs through the Portal Web GUI.
- **AI-based service troubleshooting:** The introduction of the AI-based analytics module enabled automated service analysis through AI-based algorithms, providing enhanced experiment reports and supporting automated closed-control loops actions.
- **Service Lifecycle management through GUI:** The new release of the Portal Web GUI enabled the customization of the service and service lifecycle management capabilities.

In Table 2 we summarize the features introduced by each module on each release.

Table 2 VITAL-5G Platform Module releases

Software component	VITAL-5G responsible partner	Early drop features	First full drop features
Portal Web GUI	eBOS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NetApp Blueprint onboarding • NetApp, VSB and VSD management • Create a graphical representation of the onboarded NetApp Blueprints 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vertical Service customization and Lifecycle management support • Experiment definition and lifecycle management • Monitoring data visualization through Grafana dashboards • Support for OAuth based access control mechanisms (Access Control with KeyCloak) • Visualization of site device inventory • Visualization of 5G slice instances in Slice Inventory • Monitoring Network and Infrastructure metrics from the user selected testbeds through Grafana dashboards

<p>NetApps, Services & Experiments Catalogue</p>	<p>NXW</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onboarding, query and removal of NetApp blueprints over emulated VITAL-5G testbed • Onboarding, query and removal of VSB/VSD over emulated VITAL-5G testbed • Onboarding, query and removal of EXPB/EXPD • REST APIs for the aforementioned functionalities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support for OAuth based access control mechanisms • Enhanced support for Experiment and Test Case definition • Onboarding of VNF Packages/NSDs on VITAL-5G site NFVO catalogue through OSM based driver • MINIO file storage support for NetApp package management • Automated NetApp package validation through NetApp package validator API • VITAL-5G site NFVO information retrieval through site inventory client.
<p>Service LCM</p>	<p>NXW</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Instantiation and termination of vertical services composed of one or more NetApps, with basic lifecycle management and interaction with the catalogue. • Basic instantiation on emulated VITAL-5G testbed with driver for OSM NFVO. • REST APIs for the aforementioned functionalities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access control validation through OAUTH based mechanisms • Automated management of Network Slices through Slice Inventory • VITAL-5G site NFVO Lifecycle Management integration through OSM based driver • VITAL-5G site NFVO information retrieval through site inventory client.
<p>NetApp Validator</p>	<p>BEIA</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validation of NetApp blueprint JSON syntax • Basic validation of IoT data used by the NetApp. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Re-packaged as web application • Expose OpenAPI-based REST interfaces for interaction with other components • Validation of sensor data in the facility (via interaction with multi-site inventory) • Dynamic KPI monitoring and validation from the 5G testbed
<p>Experiment LCM</p>	<p>NXW</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experiment lifecycle management functionalities for experiment creation/termination and execution over emulated VITAL-5G testbed • REST API for experiment management • Interaction with Experiment catalogue to get experiment blueprints/descriptors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access control validation through OAUTH based mechanisms • Integration with Results Analytics and AI-based diagnostics • Support for enhanced Test Case and Experiment definition • Support of experiment execution through OSM Day2 primitives

Monitoring Platform	IMEC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simple configuration of topics for network, infrastructure, service and platform KPIs • Storing metrics in the database based on the synthetic data • Initial definition of interfaces towards VITAL-5G testbed monitoring agents 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic configuration of topics for network, infrastructure, service and platform monitoring metrics • Real-time collection of metrics/KPIs using ZeroMQ queues • Fully designed unified interface towards VITAL-5G testbed monitoring agents for metric configuration and data retrieval • Per topic Publish/subscribe mechanism for data ingestion and distribution • Monitoring data visualization through Grafana panels • Topics for diagnostics event distribution
Slice Inventory	IMEC	N/A, this is the first release of the software module	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VITAL-5G Site 5G slice catalogue management through REST API. • Unified Southbound Interface (SBI) for slice lifecycle management (i.e., slice provisioning, UE attachment and dynamic modification) towards VITAL-5G site slice management agents. • Northbound API (NBI) for 5G slice allocation and querying towards VITAL-5G Platform modules.
Access control	WINGS	N/A, this is the first release of the software module	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support for OAuth based access control mechanisms (Access Control with Keycloak) • Supports RBAC model. • Keycloak Client creation for each VITAL-5G Platform component Keycloak interacts with. • Assign Roles to the corresponding users (one user could have multiple roles) • Assign granularity with extra attributes to the access token per Use Case
Multi-site inventory	NXW	N/A, this is the first release of the software module	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VITAL-5G Site IoT device Catalogue management and querying • VITAL-5G Site NFVO Information management and querying

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VITAL-5G Site Monitoring Agent information management and querying
Results analytics	WINGS	N/A, this is the first release of the software module	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ingestion of generated network, infrastructure, service, and platform metrics. • Statistical analysis of the ingested metrics. • Calculation and validation of KPIs. • Generation of threshold events based on the validation results. • Interfaces with the Monitoring platform for metric ingestion and KPI publishing. • Interface with the LCM for event propagation, as part of the closed-loop control mechanism.
AI-based diagnostics	WINGS	N/A, this is the first release of the software module	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ingestion of collected metrics and generated KPIs. • Anomaly and performance degradation detection. • Root cause analysis for the detected anomalies. • Generation of diagnostic events based on the detection results. • Interface with LCM for event propagation as part of the closed-loop control mechanism.

In Figure 1 we depict the updated diagram of the VITAL-5G platform software components, highlighting the components included in the first full release drop of the platform. It is worth to highlight the following updates in terms of the components and interfaces:

- Experiment LCM interface towards VITAL-5G testbed: Given the usage of OSM in the three testbeds of the project and after analyzing OSM (see Section 4.3.1) support for Day2 primitive execution, we decided to leverage this interface to perform the experiment configuration and execution. Therefore, the interface toward the VITAL-5G testbed now points to the NFVO and eliminates the need of the NetApp Runtime configurator module.
- NetApp Validation and Blueprint Validation merge: Given the similarities and dependencies between these two software modules, we decided to merge them together in one single software module. We now refer only to NetApp Validator.

Figure 1: Software components of VITAL-5G platform

2.1 Portal Web GUI

The VITAL-5G portal web GUI was originally based on the 5G-EVE portal GUI. At the time of the first full release, it has been completely revamped to fit the needs of the VITAL-5G project. As described in D2.1 [1], the VITAL-5G GUI will provide access to users to all the backend functionalities and tools of the VITAL-5G platform to design their experiments through the proper selection of experiments, Network Applications, and services blueprints, and to offer an intent-based service.

The GUI is designed to serve the needs of the internal experimenters (members of the consortium) as well as provide a convenient and intuitive interface for the 3rd party experimenters who wish to either onboard their own Network Applications or use the existing catalogue of the project-developed Network Applications. Through the GUI, various users will be able to access their individual account, validate their Network Applications, upload their Blueprints, view the available assets in the testbeds and trial sites (as well as view the slice allocation provided by the network operators) as well as visualise the results from the testbeds in terms of KPIs.

2.1.1 First-full-release features

The early-drop version of the VITAL-5G portal web GUI, described in deliverable D2.2 [2], was a revamped version of the Web GUI developed as part of 5G-EVE project [4] and was extended to cover the upload, visualization, and management of Network Application Blueprints. Additionally, the VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI is responsible for the KPIs visualization of the experiments conducted at each T&L trial site. We follow an agile interaction design to achieve practical and pragmatic design, short development cycles, and dynamic designs that are responsive to changing needs.

In Figure 2, we provide a visual representation of the current state of the VITAL-5G GUI with the following features implemented in the transition from the early drop to the first full release:

- Implementation of the Access Control module using KeyCloak integration
- Improved NetApp and Vertical Service Blueprint (VSB) filtering per testbed, use case or status according to the individual user's needs)
- TestCase Blueprint Management and updated Experiment Descriptors
- Implementation of the experiment Life Cycle Manager (LCM) which provides:

- Visualization of list of experiments
- Trigger instantiation/termination of experiments
- Visualization of experiment details
- Updated monitoring capabilities
- Improved visualization of VSBs in terms of graphs and linking to Network Application structure
- Provision for adding support tools in the final release. One of the tools would be the Network Application validator that is set to be released with the final operational version of the platform that would allow users to run checks in their 3rd party Network Application before uploading it on the platform.

Figure 2: The VITAL-5G portal web GUI interface

An example of the improved visualization of VSBs can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Network Applications Blueprint visualization

The capability of the platform to extract KPIs from the testbeds can be seen from the example presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Instantiation of a service and extraction of metrics

It is worth to be noted that more features are planned for M30 like the ability to visualise the 5G slices as well as direct VNF and NSD management. We are also provisioning to provide users with links to the Network Application software and APIs documentation.

2.1.2 Software diagram

The component diagram for the VITAL-5G GUI is presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5: VITAL-5G GUI component diagram

2.1.3 API and interfaces

The GUI does not have exposed APIs, but rather will connect with the centralised monitoring platform that is in charge of collecting the Network and Service KPIs and displaying them on-demand for the user, the Experiment and Service LCM, the NetApps, Services and Experiments Catalogue as well as the Blueprints Validation tool which is integral for Quality of Experience (QoE).

2.1.4 Baseline software updates

As stated in deliverable D2.2, the Web GUI developed as part of 5G-EVE project was extended to cover the upload, visualization and management of NetApp Blueprints and support a wide range of internal users and 3rd party experimenters. The updates are detailed in section 2.1.1.

2.1.5 Software assets

2.1.5.1 Repositories / Images

The GUI is released under an Apache 2 license, and the source code is available in the project GitLab repository¹.

2.1.5.2 Software structure (open source)

The VITAL-5G portal web GUI was generated using Angular CLI², version 9.1.7. The environment setup requires the installation of nodejs, the Angular modules, the project dependencies as well as the development server. Notably, Angular applications are modular and thus Angular comes with its own modularity system called NgModules. NgModules are containers for a cohesive block of code dedicated to an application domain, a workflow, or a closely related set of capabilities. They can contain components, service providers, and other code files whose scope is defined by the containing NgModule.

Every Angular application has at least one NgModule class, the root module, which is conventionally named AppModule and resides in a file named app.module.ts. To launch the VITAL-5G GUI module the application needs to be bootstrapped from the root NgModule.

Angular loads as a collection of JavaScript modules which can be thought in the context of library modules. Each Angular library name begins with the @angular prefix. They can be installed with the node package manager npm and parts of the can be imported with JavaScript import statements.

2.1.5.3 Installation

The install folder in the module repository³ contains precise installation instructions which allow any user or developer to build and execute this module.

2.2 NetApps, Services & Experiment Catalogue

As described in D2.1 [1], this module provides the NetApp, Service and Experiment catalogue management functionalities of the VITAL-5G platform. On the northbound interface it offers a REST based API, which is used by the rest of the modules of the platform to onboard, retrieve and delete NetApp packages and blueprints, Vertical Service Blueprints and Descriptors (VSB and VSD), Experiment Blueprints and Descriptors (ExpB and ExpD). The internal modules implement the logic for the synchronization with the three VITAL-5G site NFVO catalogues, and the platform internal database and file storage. Furthermore, as part of the internal workflows, this module interacts with: (i) Access Control module, to authenticate and authorize the request and retrieve user information data; (ii) NetApp Validator, to determine if the NetApp is correctly formatted and if the targeted

¹ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/portal-web-gui

² <https://github.com/angular/angular-cli>

³ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/

testbed has the proper devices described in the NetApp Blueprint; (iii) Multi-site inventory, to retrieve the VITAL-5G site NFVO endpoints and credentials.

2.2.1 First-full-release features

The early-drop version of this module, described in D2.2 [2], included initial support for NetApp, VSB/VSD, ExpB/ExpD catalogue management over an emulated VITAL-5G testbed. The first-full-release added support for:

- Access Control integration: Validation of the user roles (e.g., NetApp Developer, Vertical Service Provider, etc) to execute the management actions as established in D1.2 [3]. Validation of the descriptor ownership and use case mapping to authorize request.
- Automated NetApp Validation: Leverage the *NetApp Validator* module to provide automated NetApp Blueprint syntax validation and verify availability of the required devices in the VITAL-5G targeted site.
- File storage backend support: Integration of MinIO⁴ for enhanced file storage support, and ease access to NetApp package assets (i.e., API documentation, licenses, etc.).
- VITAL-5G site NFVO catalogue management: Support of site NFVO VNF Package and NSD catalogue management via per-site plugins, with *Multi-site inventory* integration for NFVO information retrieval.
- Support for Test Case definition and management: Management of the Test Case Blueprints and Descriptors, which provide determine the actions to execute during an experiment and to reset the environment once the experiment finishes.

2.2.2 Test Case blueprints and Experiment Descriptors

As in 5G-EVE, in VITAL-5G Test Case Blueprints (TCBs) are templates which describe the actions to be run during an experiment execution, and their input parameters. In VITAL-5G we identify three different experiment actions: (i) configuration: prepares the environment and the service for the experiment execution; (ii) execution: implements the logic of the experiment; (iii) reset: cleans the environment to prepare for another experiment execution.

In VITAL-5G the different TCB actions leverage NFVO Network Service Level LCM actions (e.g., OSM Day 2 configuration). For this reason, each TCB action is mapped to a NFVO LCM level action. The full specification of the TCB information model is described in Table 3 and Table 4

Table 3 Test Case Blueprint Information Model

Parameter	Type	Description
executionAction	NfvoLcmAction	NFVO Level Action to be executed during the experiment execution
configurationAction	NfvoLcmAction	NFVO Level Action to be executed during the experiment configuration
resetAction	NfvoLcmAction	NFVO Level Action to be executed during the experiment reset
testCaseBlueprintId	String	Identifier of the TCB
name	String	Human readable name of the TCB
version	String	Version of the TCB

⁴ <https://min.io/>

Table 4 NFVO LCM Action Information Model

Parameter	Type	Description
nfvoActionId	String	NFVO Level action identifier as specified in the VNFD/NSD
inputParameters	List<String>	List of input parameters to be provided in the Experiment Descriptor
nfvoReference	String	A reference of the NFVO level component which will execute the action (i.e. VDU, VNF, etc)

The values of the input parameters defined in the Experiment Descriptors (ExpDs), which are the templates enabling the customization of the experiment to a specific scenario. Table 5 details the information model established for ExpDs.

Table 5 Experiment Descriptor Information Model

Parameter	Type	Description
experimentDescriptorId	UUID	Identifier generated by the VITAL-5G Platform for the ExpD
experimentBlueprintId	UUID	Reference to the Experiment Blueprint
executionActionParameters	Map<String, String>	Map of execution action input parameters, where the key is the input parameter defined in the TCB and the key is the custom value
configActionParameters	Map<String, String>	Map of configuration action input parameters, where the key is the input parameter defined in the TCB and the key is the custom value
resetActionParameters	Map<String, String>	Map of reset input parameters, where the key is the input parameter defined in the TCB and the key is the custom value
name	String	Descriptive name of the ExpD
version	String	Version of the ExpD

2.2.3 Software diagram

In Figure 6 we depict the internal software architecture of this module, highlighting the initial release of each internal submodule, where R1 corresponds to the early-drop and R2 to the first-full-version.

Figure 6: NetApp, Service and Experiment Catalogue internal software architecture

As described in D2.1 [1] and D2.2 [2] this module is a Spring-Boot based Java application. The logic implemented by each internal module is as follows:

- **REST Controller:** As described in D2.2 [2], this module implements REST endpoints enabling the catalogue management operations, performing an initial format validation and the validation of the user credentials before sending the request to the catalogue service module. The source code of this module can be found inside the *it.nextworks.catalogue.nbi* package inside the *vital-5g-catalogue* project. The first-full-version release updated this module to include the access control mechanisms and support for NetApp VNF Package onboarding.
- **Catalogue Service:** This module performs an in-depth validation of the request, leveraging the *NetApp Validator* module, interacting with the VITAL-5G site through the NFVO Sync Manager module for the management of the VNF Packages and NSDs associated with the NetApps and VSBs. Moreover, this module interacts with the JPA-based repositories for the management of the database associated entries, and with the *File Storage Client* for the management of the files associated with the NetApps. The source code of this module can be found inside the *it.nextworks.catalogue.services* package inside the *vital-5g-catalogue* project. The first-full-version release added support for access control verification, and integration with the *NetApp Validator* module.
- **JPA-Based repositories:** This module mediates between the Catalogue Service and the database providing simplified interfaces for the management of the database records. The source code of this module can be found inside the *it.nextworks.catalogue.repos* package inside the *vital-5g-catalogue* project.
- **NFVO Synchronizer and NFVO Catalogue Service:** These two modules mediate between the internal catalogue components and the NFVO VNF and NSD catalogues of the VITAL-5G testbeds, providing a simplified and unified interface, and automated syncing the NFVO catalogue based on the NetApp and Vertical Service Blueprint catalogue operations. The source code of this module can be found inside the *it.nextworks.catalogue.sbi* package inside the *vital-5g-catalogue* project. This release includes per-site plugins implementing the site-specific management logic (based on OSM), and the interaction with the *Multi-site inventory* for site NFVO information retrieval.
- **SQL database:** The database created to support the registries associated with the different catalogues.
- **File Storage Client and MINIO:** MinIO is a high-performance and high-availability object storage platform which is used to store and manage the files associated with a NetApp (i.e., NetApp package and blueprint,

licenses, software documentation, etc). The File Storage Client implements the logic to interact with MinIO to sync the catalogue management operations with the storage backend.

- Multi-site inventory client: Implements a REST client to consume the *Multi-site inventory* API to retrieve the testbed capabilities, and the NFVO information.
- NetApp Validator client: Implements a REST client to consume the *NetApp Validator* API to validate the NetApp blueprint syntax and validate device availability in the targeted site.

2.2.4 API and interfaces

The API of this module is described in D2.2 [2], and the full specification is available in OpenAPI format⁵. The modifications introduced for the first-full-version release added support for NetApp VNF Package passing, and error codes associated with access control validations.

2.2.5 Baseline software updates

The NetApp, Service and Experiment Catalogue module used the 5G-EVE Portal Catalogue module (see 5G-EVE D4.1 [5], for further details) as software baseline. In this sense, this module has been designed using the 5G-EVE Portal Catalogue software architecture, information models and internal catalogue management workflows as starting point. In terms of software code, most of Catalogue Service, REST controller and JPA-repositories of the 5G-EVE Portal Catalogue have been re-used and extended for the implementation of the VITAL-5G catalogue. In parallel, new data models (with the respective JPA-repositories and REST controllers) and new internal modules have been developed from scratch in order to implement the NetApp-specific functionalities and enable the integration with the rest of the VITAL-5G platform. In details, the software updates and the new implementations are the following:

- **[New implementation]** Development of NetApp blueprint data model, REST controllers and catalogue services for onboarding/queries of NetApp packages and blueprints, and JPA repositories related to the NetApp blueprint data model. The concept of NetApps was not present in 5G EVE, and therefore all the related functionalities in the NetApp catalogue have been added in VITAL-5G. Where possible, some of the common information elements of the VSB data models were reused and extended.
- **[Software update]** Changes in the information models of Vertical Service and Experiment Blueprints and Descriptors. In 5G EVE, the experiments and vertical service instances were tightly coupled, and in practice a service instance was dependent on a specific experiment. In VITAL-5G we removed this dependency, decoupling vertical service and experiment instances, so that the user can directly manage the service lifecycle without any binding to experiment executions. At the catalogue level, this has implications on the VSB, ExpBs and TCBs data models, which have been updated (together with the respective JPA repositories, where needed).
- **[New implementation]** Development and integration of NFVO Synch Manager. In 5G EVE the synchronization between the 5G EVE Portal Catalogue and the testbeds' NFVO catalogues was performed by the 5G EVE InterWorking Layer (IWL). In VITAL-5G this functionality has been moved directly in the VITAL-5G Catalogue. This required the development of the internal module logic, the driver to interact with the OSM catalogues deployed in each testbed and the integration in the catalogue management workflows.
- **[New implementation]** File storage backend for local storage of NetApp packages. In order to ease the management and access to the NetApp package assets (i.e., the whole package or the single files of documentation, API specifications, licenses), a MINIO file storage backend was introduced as part of the NetApp catalogue. In terms of implementation, this required the integration of an S3 client library to

⁵ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/OpenOnlineRepository/-/blob/main/API/VITAL-5G%20open%20repository%20OpenAPI.json

interact with MINIO and the update of the logic at the catalogue management workflows to process, extract and store the package files.

- **[New implementation and software update]** Integration with the specific services of the VITAL-5G platform. In the VITAL-5G platform, the VITAL-5G catalogue needs to interact in client mode with two new modules: (i) multi-site inventory for the storage of per-testbed information (see Section 2.8) and (ii) NetApp validator for the NetApp blueprint syntax validation and overall validation of the NetApp package (see Section 2.4). The required REST clients have been implemented, starting from the autogenerated code of the related OpenAPI, and their invocation has been integrated in the catalogue services' workflows.

2.2.6 Software assets

2.2.6.1 Repositories / Images

This module is released as open source, using an Apache 2.0 license, and the source code is available in the project GitLab repository⁶.

2.2.6.2 Software structure

As described in D2.2 [2], the code is divided mainly in two maven projects:

- Information models and interfaces (*vital-5g-catalogue-interfaces*): This maven project contains specifies the information elements (i.e., blueprints and descriptors), and the interfaces describing the catalogue operations. This project is meant to be used by the other modules of the platform in order to interact with this catalogue.
- Catalogue application (*vital-5g-catalogue*): This a spring-boot based maven project, implementing the modules depicted in Figure 6, using the *vital-5g-catalogue-interfaces* as a dependency, and is responsible for providing the Java executable JAR package.

The repository also contains a project with the NetApp Validator client (*netapp-validator-client*), which contains a client automatically generated from the OpenAPI specification of the NetApp Validator module. This project is also used as a dependency in the *vital-5g-catalogue*.

2.2.6.3 Installation

The install folder in the module repository⁷ contains the installation instructions and docker files which allow to build and execute this module using Docker.

2.3 Service LCM

As described in D2.1 [1], this module provides the vertical service lifecycle management capabilities (i.e., instantiation, termination, scaling and querying), through a REST-based interface. In this sense, this module implements the logic for the Vertical Service Instance management, including the interaction with the: (i) *Monitoring platform* for the management of the monitoring metrics to be retrieved; (ii) *Results analytics AI-based diagnostics*, for the signalling of the experiment execution and termination; (iii) Interaction with *Multi-site slice inventory* for the retrieval of the available 5G slices and the provisioning depending on the site capabilities; (iv) the VITAL-5G site NFVO for the lifecycle management of the Network Services associated with the Vertical Services. Internally this module implements the databases containing the records associated with the vertical services instances and implements the finite state machine described in D2.1 [1].

⁶ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/OpenOnlineRepository

⁷ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/OpenOnlineRepository/-/tree/main/install

2.3.1 First-full-release features

The early-drop release of this module supported basic vertical service lifecycle capabilities (i.e., instantiation, querying and termination) over an emulated VITAL-5G testbed NFVO LCM interface. The first-full-version release added support for the following features:

- Access control validation: Integration with the *Access control* module for role and user use case verification.
- Automated management of Network Slices: Integration with *Multi-site slice inventory* for the retrieval or provisioning of network slices depending on the site capabilities.
- VITAL-5G site NFVO Lifecycle Management integration: Automated Network Service Lifecycle management capabilities on the three VITAL-5G sites, including NFVO information retrieval from the *Multi-site inventory*.
- Support for vertical service scaling/modification for closed-loop automation: Implementation of REST-based interface (to be used by other platform modules) and logic to enable automated service scaling. Implementation of scaling policies catalogue and logic for automated service scaling.

2.3.2 Software diagram

In Figure 7 we depict the internal software architecture of this module, as established in D2.1 [1], highlighting the initial release of each internal component. It is important to highlight the software architecture has been extended to adapt to the updated software workflows (described in Section 4.2). The functionality and the updates introduced in each internal module is as follows:

- REST Controller: As described in D2.1 [1], this module implements the REST server responsible for receiving and validating the service lifecycle management requests, and forward the request to the Service LCM Engine. The source code of this module is located in the *it.nextworks.lcm.vs.nbi* package of the *vital-5g-service-lcm* project. For the first-full-version release this submodule was updated to enable the access control verification and support vertical service modification/scaling procedures.
- Service LCM Engine: This module implements the logic to process all the service lifecycle management requests, validating the messages, creating instance specific service managers, and forwarding the messages towards the specific manager. The source code of this module is located in the *it.nextworks.lcm.vs.engine* package of the *vital-5g-service-lcm* project.
- Vertical Service Instance (VSI) Manager: As described in D2.2 [2], this module is responsible for the lifecycle management requests for one specific service instance, implementing the finite state machine associated to the instance, and interacting with other modules in order to trigger the actions associated with the different lifecycle management events. In this release, this module has been updated to enable the interaction with: (i) VS Monitoring Service, for the creation/deletion of the monitoring metrics to be collected by the *Monitoring platform*; (ii) Multi-site inventory service, enabling the retrieval of the VITAL-5G site slicing capabilities, (iii) Multi-site slice inventory service, for the allocation/de-allocation of the required slice and attachment of the UEs to the correspondent slices (depending on the site capabilities); (iv) VSI Control Service, to establish the conditions and the actions to be triggered to support automated vertical service modification based on the NetApp and VSB information. The source code of this module is located in the *it.nextworks.lcm.vs.manager* package of the *vital-5g-service-lcm* project.
- VSI Record Manager: This module mediates with the Postgres DB⁸ to manage the service instance records. The source code of this module is located in the *it.nextworks.lcm.vs.repo* package of the *vital-5g-service-lcm* project.
- Open online repository Service & Client: As established in D2.2 [2], these two modules implement the logic for the retrieval of the NetApps and Vertical Service Blueprints and Descriptors from the *NetApp*,

⁸ <https://www.postgresql.org/>

Services and Experiments Catalogue via a REST client. The source code of this module is located in the *it.nextworks.lcm.vs.sbi.catalogue* package of the *vital-5g-service-lcm* project.

- NFVO Service & NFVO client: As established in D2.2 [2], these modules mediate between the VSI Manager and the specific testbed NFVO supporting a unified interface for the network service lifecycle management operations. This release added support for network service scaling in support of the vertical service scaling procedures. The source code of this module is located in the *it.nextworks.lcm.vs.sbi.nfvo* package of the *vital-5g-service-lcm* project.
- Multi-site inventory service & client: This module is used to mediate between the internal components of the service lifecycle management, and the *Multi-site inventory*. In this release this submodule supports the retrieval of the testbed NFVO information and slicing capabilities. The source code of this module is located in the *it.nextworks.lcm.vs.sbi.siteinventory* package of the *vital-5g-service-lcm* project.
- Multi-site 5G slice inventory service and client: Implements the client for the *Multi-site 5G slice inventory* which enables the allocation/de-allocation of the required slices and the attachment of UEs to 5G slices. The source code of this module is located in the *it.nextworks.lcm.vs.sbi.sliceinventory* package of the *vital-5g-service-lcm* project.
- VSI RuntimeAction service: The objective of this module is to trigger automated vertical service lifecycle management actions (e.g., service scaling, transport network re-configuration, etc) according to the runtime actions configured on the VSB to support closed-control loops. For this, this module subscribes to the correspondent topics on the *Monitoring platform*, and automatically triggers the requested action through the VSI LCM Engine. We refer to Section 4 for more details regarding the workflow. The source code of this module is located in the *it.nextworks.lcm.vs.control* package of the *vital-5g-service-lcm* project.

Figure 7: Service Lifecycle Manager internal software architecture

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No 101016567

2.3.3 API and interfaces

The API of this module has been described in D2.1 [1] and is available in OpenAPI format⁹.

2.3.4 Baseline software updates

The Service LCM module used the 5G-EVE Experiment LCM module (see 5G-EVE D4.1 [5], for further details) as software baseline. From this perspective, this module has been designed using the 5G-EVE Experiment LCM software architecture, API and internal instance management workflows as starting point. In this manner, most of vertical service lifecycle management engine and managers, REST controller and JPA-repositories software code of the 5G-EVE Portal module has been re-used. In this regard, the main modifications performed was the decoupling of the vertical service and experiment lifecycle management. In particular for this module all the experiment instance related workflows were removed. In parallel, updates and new implementations were performed to interact to VITAL-5G specific modules. In detail:

- **[Software update]** Decouple of vertical service and experiment instance lifecycle management: The REST API was updated to enable vertical service instance management. The internal module workflows and messages were updated to eliminate the dependency with experiment instance specific information. Experiment instance specific workflows (e.g., execution, termination) were completely removed.
- **[New implementation]** NetApp catalogue client: The NetApp catalogue client to interact with the catalogue module has been developed using the VSB/ExpB clients available from 5G-EVE as reference.
- **[New implementation]** NFVO Lifecycle Management: In 5G-EVE the lifecycle management of the network services was performed through a ETSI SOL based lifecycle management interface implemented by the 5G-EVE InterWorking Layer (IWL), which was ultimately responsible of implementing the drivers towards the different sites. In VITAL-5G we use a driver-based approach at the Service LCM level to directly interact with the testbed NFVOs. This required the development of the NFVO Service and specific clients.
- **[New implementation]** Development of closed-control loop actuation support: In VITAL-5G new submodule has been developed from scratch to trigger the actuation phase of the closed-control loops (see Section 2.3.2). Moreover, Network Slice and Network Service scaling workflows and API have been introduced to implement the actuation phase.
- **[New implementation]** 5G slice management/attachment: In 5G-EVE the Experiment LCM module passed the 5G slice profile characteristics to the 5G-EVE IWL module as part of the network service instantiation request. The 5G-EVE IWL then responsible for the provisioning/configuration/attachment of the 5G slices to the proper endpoints of the services. In VITAL-5G this is done through the Multi-site 5G slice inventory which is triggered by the Service LCM. The workflow and code related to this has been completely developed within VITAL-5G.
- **[Software update]** Update of monitoring client libraries: The Monitoring Platform has been developed from scratch in VITAL-5G, and therefore the API and consequently the client modules have been updated. In this case, autogenerated client libraries were created based on the OpenAPI specification of the Monitoring Platform.
- **[New implementation]** Support for dynamic NFVO information retrieval: In VITAL-5G we use the multi-site inventory module to store information about the different sites. In particular we use the multi-site inventory to store the testbed NFVO endpoints, credentials, and VIM accounts. The Service LCM was extended to include new client libraries and support the retrieval of this information as part of the lifecycle management workflows.

⁹ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/service-lcm/-/blob/main/API/VITAL-5G%20vertical%20service%20LCM.json

2.3.5 Software assets

2.3.5.1 Repositories / Images

This module is released under an Apache 2 license, and the source code is available in the project GitLab repository¹⁰.

2.3.5.2 Software structure

The code is divided mainly divided in two maven projects:

- *Vital-5g-service-lcm-interfaces*: This project contains the Java classes implementing the interfaces and the information elements used to interact with this module. It is mean to be used as a dependency by other Java based modules interacting with this module.
- *Vital-5g-service-lcm*: This contains the logic of the sub-modules of the service lifecycle manager, as detailed previously. It uses the *vital-5g-service-lcm-interfaces* as a dependency, implements the interfaces and uses the information elements of this latter project.

The repository also contains another maven project, *vital-5g-monitoring-client*, which implements the REST client and information models required to interface with the API.

2.3.5.3 Installation

The install folder in the module repository¹¹ contains the installation instructions and docker files which allow to build and execute this module using Docker.

2.4 NetApp Validator

As presented in D2.1, the NetApp validator is based on a static validator before NetApp runtime together with a dynamic KPI monitoring and validator tool at onboarding/runtime. During the first-full release of the NetApp validator tool, the static validator tool is enhanced and basic dynamic KPI monitoring is implemented with monitoring parameters obtained from the 5G testbed. Its main functionality is to validate the blueprint of the NetApp according to the static features as well as the dynamic 5G network parameters. Figure 8 shows the positioning of the component within the overall tool high level architecture.

2.4.1 First-full-release features

The modifications introduced for the first-full-version release added re-packaging as web application deployed in a container, validation of sensor data availability in the facility (due to interaction with multi-site inventory component which holds the sensors deployed within a testbed necessary for running the experiment), and OpenAPIs for calling the validator either for blueprint or IoT data validation. Moreover, basic KPI monitoring and validation from the 5G testbed is enabled. Specifically, the following data can be retrieved via the monitoring platform:

- system metrics (CPU, RAM etc.) from the compute nodes running the NetApps
- bandwidth
- E2E latency on RAN

¹⁰ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/service-lcm

¹¹ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_platform/service-lcm/-/tree/main/install

2.4.2 Software diagram

Figure 8: 5G NetApp validator tool high-level architecture

2.4.3 API and interfaces

An illustration of the API of this module is shown in Figure 9, and the full specification is available in OpenAPI format¹²

NetApp Validator API 1.0.0 OAS3

Simple API for calling the VITAL-5G NetApp validator

[Contact the developer](#)

default ^

POST `/api/blueprint/validate/syntax` Validate the syntax of the JSON blueprint v

POST `/api/blueprint/validate/sensors` Validate the sensor list of the JSON blueprint v

POST `/api/blueprint/validate` Validate the JSON blueprint v

Schemas ^

Response ←

Figure 9: NetApp validator API

¹² https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_platform/blueprint-validator/-/tree/main/API

2.4.4 Baseline software updates

The NetApp validator is based on the 5G-EVE blueprint validator, but with several major enhancements. In particular, the following have been performed so that the module may work with VITAL-5G models and interact with other VITAL-5G modules:

- **[Software update]** Most of the validation procedure has been reused, but it has been adapted to validating the NetApp against the models (blueprints, descriptors, etc.) developed in VITAL-5G
- **[Software update]** The baseline blueprint validator from 5G-EVE was a standalone Java application packaged as a JAR file that had to be executed from command line. The blueprint validator simply performed syntax validation, without any validation of testbed sensors or dynamic KPI monitoring and validation.
- **[New implementation]** The NetApp validator has been redesigned to run as a web application, packaged as war file and deployed in a tomcat container
- **[New implementation]** Open APIs have been developed for calling the NetApp validator from other clients (internal or external)
- **[New implementation]** Interaction between the multi-site inventory and the NetApp validator is enabled such that the validator can validate that the requested sensors exist in the facility where the NetApp is deployed/onboarded.
- **[New implementation]** Support for interaction with the monitoring platform for retrieving 5G testbed KPIs.

2.4.5 Software assets

2.4.5.1 Repositories / Images

This module is released under an Apache 2 license, and the source code is available in the project GitLab repository¹³

2.4.5.2 Software structure (open source)

The code is contained inside a maven project inside the *src* folder of the repository.

2.4.5.3 Installation

The install folder in the module repository¹⁴ contains the installation instructions and docker files which allow to build and execute this module using Docker

¹³ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_platform/blueprint-validator

¹⁴ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_platform/blueprint-validator/-/tree/main/install

2.5 Experiment LCM

The Experiment Lifecycle Manager (LCM), as described in D2.1 [1], is the VITAL-5G component responsible for the creation and execution of experiments to experimentally evaluate the overall service functionality and performance in the 5G-enabled testbeds. This module REST-based API on its northbound interface to allow VITAL-5G experimenters to request new experiments, configure and launch their execution, retrieve information on their status and results, and terminate them.

2.5.1 First-full-release features

The early-drop version of this module focused on providing experiment lifecycle management capabilities over an emulated interface towards the VITAL-5G testbeds. In the first-full-version release the focus was set on the integration with: (i) Access control module for the validation and authentication of the user credentials; (ii) Results Analytics and Monitoring modules for the creation of experiment specific metrics, and the signalling of the experiment execution termination to the Results Analytics module; (iii) NFVO client with support for the execution of experiment scripts.

2.5.2 Software diagram

The internal software architecture of this module is depicted in Figure 10. The figure also highlights the initial release for each one of the internal components. The functionality of each of these internal modules is as follows:

- **REST Controller:** Implements a REST server supporting the northbound interface of the module enabling experiment management, leveraging the *Access Control* for the authentication and authorization of the incoming request. The source code of this module can be found inside the *it.nextworks.experiment.nbi* package inside *vital-5g experiment-lcm* project. This new release of this internal module added support access control validation.
- **Experiment Execution Coordinator:** Processes all the lifecycle management requests coming from the REST Controller, creating, and interacting with the specific Experiment Instance Managers, which are in charge of the lifecycle management of the single experiment execution, and with the database used for the persistence of experiment data. The source code of this module can be found inside the *it.nextworks.experiment.coordinator* package inside the *vital-5g experiment-lcm* project.
- **Experiment Instance Manager:** Handles the lifecycle management of a specific experiment instance following the finite state described in D2.1 [1], and it interacts with the external components of the VITAL-5G Platform. In this release the development focused on the integration of the *Monitoring platform*, *Results Analytics*, and execution of test scripts through the *NFVO client*. The source code of this module can be found inside the *it.nextworks.experiment.manager* package inside the *vital-5g experiment-lcm* project.
- **JPA-based repositories & SQL database:** Hold and provide access to the persistent experiment instance records, containing the information about the experiment instance (i.e., experiment status, vertical service instance id, etc)
- **Experiment LCM SBI services:** Implement the interaction with the other VITAL-5G platform components: (i) Open online repository client, for the retrieval of Experiment Blueprints and Descriptors (ExpBs and ExpDs); (ii) Service LCM, to retrieve service instance information and lock the instance for experimentation; (iii) Monitoring Client, for the configuration of experiment specific metrics; (iv) Results Analytics Client, to signal the execution and termination of experiments; (v) NFVO client, for the retrieval of network service instance information and execution of test scripts through Day2 actions.

Figure 10: Experiment LCM internal software architecture

2.5.3 API and interfaces

The API definition for this module has been documented in D2.1 [1] and D2.2 [2], and is available in OpenAPI format¹⁵.

2.5.4 Baseline software updates

The Experiment LCM module of VITAL-5G used the 5G-EVE Service LCM and Experiment Execution Manager as initial software baseline. In this sense, this module inherited the internal software architecture, and workflows of these two modules. From the code perspective, most of the REST Controller, Experiment Execution Coordinator, Experiment Instance Manager and JPA-based repositories was re-used from the original modules. The updates and modifications to the software baseline are as follows:

- **[Software Update]** Experiment Lifecycle management and execution decoupling: In 5G-EVE [4] the experiment and instance were tightly coupled. In VITAL-5G, on the other side, we decoupled the experiment instance management and execution. In terms of code this implied the extraction of the experiment instance management workflows from the 5G EVE Service LCM. In a similar manner, the 5G EVE experiment execution workflows were integrated within this module.
- **[Software Update]** Test Case Blueprint (TCB) and Experiment Descriptor (ExpD) client and information model update: In VITAL-5G we use updated TCBs and ExpDs (see Section 2.2.2), and this required updates in the client libraries and in the workflows.
- **[New implementation]** Support of actions through NFVO Day2 actions: In 5G EVE Robot Framework¹⁶ and Jenkins¹⁷ were used in combination to support the execution of custom scripts for the experiment configuration, execution and reset. In VITAL-5G experiment scripts are supported through NFVO Day2

¹⁵ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_platform/experiment-lcm/-/tree/main/API

¹⁶ <https://robotframework.org/>

¹⁷ <https://www.jenkins.io/>

primitives defined in the Test Case Blueprints. This required the development of a NFVO Client supporting Day2 primitive execution.

- **[Software Update]** Updated Monitoring Libraries: In VITAL-5G a new monitoring platform has been developed from scratch, offering a new API. For this reason, the monitoring client libraries were updated using autogenerated code based on the OpenAPI specification.

2.5.5 Software assets

2.5.5.1 Repositories / Images

This module is released as open source, using an Apache 2.0 license, and the source code is available in the project GitLab repository¹⁸.

2.5.5.2 Software structure

The code fully contained inside a maven project inside the *src* folder of the repository.

2.5.5.3 Installation

The install folder in the module repository¹⁹ contains the installation instructions and docker files which allow to build and execute this module using Docker.

2.6 Access Control

The Access control module is responsible to provide user management and authentication/authorization to other modules. This component relies on Keycloak, which is an Identity and Access Management service to store users, generate and refresh access tokens that belong to each user. The mechanism followed for the purposes of the VITAL-5G project is Role Based Access Control (RBAC).

2.6.1 First-full-release features

The authentication process is token-based, which means that registered users are able to obtain an access token, valid for a specific period, which will allow them to have access to specific resources from other back-end components. Together with the access token, they obtain a “refresh token”, whose main goal is to allow users to obtain a new access token once it is expired. The Access token also contains a list of the project’s use-cases as an extra attribute in order to put an additional granularity to the Access Control mechanism.

Regarding the authorization part the Access Control component provides roles (e.g., NetApp Developer, Vertical Service Provider, etc), which usually identify a type or category of user and groups that usually are used to define users with different roles. Both roles and groups are assigned to specific users through JSON Web Tokens (JWT) in order to be able, determine their permissions over certain backend resources. So far, the components that have been currently integrated with Access Control are vertical service lifecycle management (LCM) and NetApps, Services & Experiment Catalogue for role and user case verification.

¹⁸ <https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G Platform/experiment-lcm/-/tree/main/src>

¹⁹ <https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G Platform/experiment-lcm/-/tree/main/install>

Figure 11: Sequence diagram of Access Control Mechanism

In terms of configuration one realm called vital5g has been created that manages a set of users, credentials, roles, and groups. Each backend component (e.g., NetAppCatalogue, NetAppValidation etc.) is registered as a client to Keycloak in order to validate access tokens included from client requests and retrieve information about the owner of the token (Roles and Groups). The existing Keycloak’s clients that are currently supported are:

1. Service LCM
2. NetApp Catalogue
3. NetApp Validation
4. Monitoring Platform
5. Portal GUI

For VITAL-5G purposes, it was necessary to define roles in Keycloak to achieve RBAC model. These roles were defined at realm level, and they will be assigned to each user upon his registration. It allows creating isolated groups of applications and users. VITAL-5G roles are described in detail at D1.1/2 and are showed to the following table:

Table 6 Roles for the VITAL-5G experimentation process

Roles	Description
Experimenter	Experimenters are validating new NetApps or services.
NetApp_Developer	Developers of NetApps. They use the platform to onboard their own NetApps.
Platform_admin	Administrator of the VITAL-5G Open Platform.
Platform_Technician	They are responsible for the support in the design and execution of experiments and KPIs analysis.

Testbed_Admin	Administrators of one of the VITAL-5G testbeds, responsible for the overall testbed design, deployment, and maintenance.
T&L_Site_Infrastructure_Manager	They are responsible for the infrastructure and equipment to be used in the experiment.
Vertical_Service_Provider	Developers of vertical-specific services, which can be built composing NetApps and VNFs available in the VITAL-5G catalogue

The use cases are included to the access token of each user as an attribute as it is seen in Figure 12:

Figure 12: Keycloak Instance with the associated use-case to the user

Each use case as described at D1.2(Section 3) are included at each user’s token. Use case leaders agreed with the following naming of each use case:

- V5G-UC1-AUTOMATED-VESSEL-TRANSPORT
- V5G-UC2-ASSISTED-NAVIGATION
- V5G-UC3-FREIGHT-LOGISTICS

Keycloak has been configured to load the required certificate infrastructure using files in PEM format in order to active HTTPS endpoints. The certificates that are currently been used are self-signed.

2.6.2 API and interfaces

The authentication and authorization protocol that is used is OAuth2²⁰.

2.6.3 Baseline software updates

One of the base differences between the two implementations is that this component does not use a custom proxy in front of Keycloak, as was done in 5G-EVE, to communicate through an API with all other modules. The current solution is based on a dockerized version of Keycloak that allows RBAC to provide token-based authentication/authorization mechanisms.

²⁰ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/OAuth>

2.6.4 Software assets

2.6.4.1 Installation

The Access Control module relies on the open-source and freely available Keycloak version 16.1.1 which can be downloaded from docker hub. The install folder in the module repository contains the installation instructions and docker files which allow to build and execute this module using Docker.

2.7 Slice inventory

The Slice Inventory component is a management backend software component in charge of i) storing the information about the available 5G slices in each of the three 5G testbeds; ii) dynamic provisioning and management of 5G slices and attachment of UEs depending on the testbed capabilities; iii) selection of the 5G slice given the vertical service requirements. The stored information includes the lists of available slices per testbed, their profile characteristics, and subscribers attached to a particular slice (if available on the testbed). Such information is exposed towards the other components in the VITAL-5G Portal Backend and the Open Online Repository for the purpose of selecting the optimal slice for the vertical service and NetApp deployment, mapping the vertical service and NetApp requirements to the capabilities of the available 5G slices.

This VITAL-5G platform component is developed as Java Spring Boot application with Postgres database.

2.7.1 First-full-release features

As illustrated in Figure 13, the Slice Inventory component has a quite simple design, which consists of two main components: Slice Manager and Slice Storage. Thus, the features that are adopted in this release are shown below.

- **Dynamic retrieval of 5G slice profile characteristics (Slice Manager):** Once the slice is configured on the 5G testbed, either in a pre-configured or dynamic manner, the slice profile characteristics of this slice need to be reported to the Slice inventory. The overview of slice profile parameters is shown in Section 2.7.2, Table 7. The main goal of this component is to provide an up-to-date overview of available slices to any party (e.g., VITAL-5G Platform users) that is interested in implementing the NetApps and deploying them using the available 5G slices in a particular testbed. As shown in Figure 58, in the message sequence chart for the Slice inventory component, managing the availability of network slices in the 5G testbed enables reporting the status and configuration parameters of the newly created 5G slices, or reporting updates in the configuration parameters of the existing 5G slices (if supported by 5G testbed).
- **Storing 5G slice-related information (Slice Storage):** All the slice-related information (configuration parameters, subscribers attached to it, testbed capabilities) retrieved from the 5G testbeds is stored in the Slice inventory database, as shown in Figure 58 and Figure 59. This way, an up-to-date overview of available slices can be retrieved from the Slice inventory by any external entity querying slice-related information (details shown in Figure 59).
- **Lifecycle management of network slices (Slice Manager):** Depending on the capabilities of the VITAL-5G testbeds, the slice inventory module is using its southbound interface to perform lifecycle management of network slices (slice provisioning, UE attachment, dynamic slice configuration), by sending corresponding management requests towards slice management agents on each of the testbeds.
- **Slice allocation and querying (Slice Manager):** Once the experiment is launched and vertical service is on-boarded, it is important to select the corresponding slice that will be used for the service deployment. The Slice inventory offers interfaces that enable querying of the available 5G slices that are currently deployed in the testbeds, as well as the allocation of the 5G slice that can be used for a specific vertical service (either dynamically or in a pre-defined manner). Thus, for the purpose of slice provisioning, Service LCM is sending requests towards the Slice inventory, querying the status of pre-

configured network slices and checking their slice profile characteristics. If there is a slice that suffices the requirements, UE will be attached to it (if supported by the VITAL-5G testbed). Otherwise, a new slice will be provisioned, or the existing ones will be dynamically modified to meet the provisioning requirements (if supported by the VITAL-5G testbed).

The data handled by Slice inventory component can be accessed by any VITAL-5G component or user (including 3rd party experimenters), since the slicing capabilities from each of the available 5G testbeds should be known by those VITAL-5G components (e.g., Service LCM) when requesting the resources needed for the deployment. These requests are handled by the northbound interface for allocation and querying of available slice profiles.

The communication between the Slice inventory and other entities (slice plugins on each of the testbeds, or external components) is purely REST-based, and as such, it is invoked via southbound interface when: i) a new slice is configured, ii) the configuration of an existing slice is updated, iii) users need to be attached to a particular slice, iv) slice needs to be reconfigured based on the decisions made by VITAL-5G platform components (closed-loop operation).

2.7.2 Software diagram

In Figure 13, the high-level architecture of the Slice inventory component is presented. As already described in the previous section, the Slice inventory consists of the two main architectural elements, i.e., i) Slice Manager that is responsible for handling all REST calls, logic for processing the data retrieved from the three testbeds, and performing slice lifecycle management, and ii) Slice Storage that is storing the data in the particular table within the Slice database.

When it comes to Slice inventory operations, they highly depend on the type of the 5G testbed and its capabilities. To fine tune the operation based on those capabilities, a table `Testbed_capability` is created in the database (presented in D3.2), thereby storing the information about: i) Dynamic slice provisioning, ii) UE attachment/detachment to/from a network slice, and iii) Dynamic slice modification for supporting closed-loop control operations. As not all three testbeds support the same set of capabilities, Slice inventory is keeping track of each of the capabilities separately, and it uses this information (stored in the Table `Testbed_capabilities`) to process the REST requests and adjust the response based on the testbed type (BE, RO, GR).

Figure 13: High-level architecture of the Slice inventory component.

Table 7 Slice profile parameters.

Type of network slice	Slice profile parameters	Description
URLLC	Latency	The required maximum latency in ms.
	Jitter	The maximum supported jitter in ms.
	expDataRateUL	The required data rate in Mbps on the uplink.
	expDataRateDL	The required data rate in Mbps on the downlink.
eMBB	expDataRateUL	The required data rate in Mbps on the uplink.
	expDataRateDL	The required data rate in Mbps on the downlink.
	areaTrafficCapUL	The required area capacity uplink data rate in Mbps/m ² .
	areaTrafficCapDL	The required area capacity downlink data rate in Mbps/m ² .
	userDensity	The required user density in users/m ² .
	uESpeed	The average user equipment speed in m/s.

2.7.3 API and interfaces

Table 8 Slice inventory interfaces

#	REST API	Payload
1	sliceParameters/urllc	<pre>{ "sliceId": "AntwerpUrllc01", "site": "Antwerp", "latency": 15, "jitter": 1, "expDataRateUL": 100, "expDataRateDL": 100 }</pre>
2	sliceParameters/embb	<pre>{ "sliceId": "AntwerpEmbb01", "site": "Antwerp", "expDataRateUL": 200, "expDataRateDL": 200, "areaTrafficCapUL": 200, "areaTrafficCapDL": 200, "userDensity": 200, "userSpeed": 80 }</pre>
3	sliceUE/attach	<pre>{ "ueId": "TercofinII", "sliceId": "AntwerpEmbb01", }</pre>
4	sliceUE/detach	<pre>{ "ueId": "TercofinII", "sliceId": "AntwerpUrllc01", }</pre>

2.7.4 Baseline software updates

This software module is a new module designed and developed for the purpose of collecting up-to-date network slice information from all three 5G testbeds. Its design and development are entirely performed within the VITAL-5G project.

2.7.5 Software assets

2.7.5.1 Repositories / Images

The VITAL-5G Slice Inventory component is not open source. To facilitate the integration between the Slice Inventory and Slice Plugins on each of the testbeds, a REST-based communication is used. Unlike in the case of the centralized monitoring platform where an influx of data is being received at any moment, the requests exchanged between the Slice inventory and 5G testbeds are sporadic and happen only if there is a new slice created or if there is any update on the slice configuration. Although the component of the Slice inventory is not open source, the public APIs can be accessed by any external component, as illustrated in Figure 59, in order to list the existing slices in the 5G testbeds, and if available, to get the list of subscribers attached to a particular slice.

2.7.5.2 Software structure (open source)

This component is not open source.

2.7.5.3 Installation

The installation folder in the module repository contains all the install instructions. This Spring based Java application is using Maven 3.8 to run, and it requires PostgreSQL 13 or higher, and Grafana v9 or higher. The current version of the VITAL-5G Slice inventory component will be on a VM in the Orange testbed.

2.8 Multi-site inventory

As described in D2.1 [1], this module aims to act as a centralized inventory of the VITAL-5G site information, holding per-site records of: (i) Devices available (i.e., IoT sensors, gateways, etc); (ii) NFVO credentials and endpoints; (iii) 5G Slicing capabilities and endpoints; (iv) Endpoints for the site monitoring agents. This module exposes a REST interface which is used by the other platform modules to query the inventory catalogue.

2.8.1 First-full-release features

This module has been first released with the first-full-version of the VITAL-5G platform, offering the following capabilities:

- Management and querying of site devices: Support for creation, deletion and querying of devices.
- Management and querying of site NFVO information: Support for creation, deletion and querying of site NFVO information (i.e., NFVO type, endpoints, credentials and external networks)
- Management and querying of site monitoring agents: Support for creation, deletion and querying of site Monitoring agents endpoints
- Management and querying of site 5G slice capabilities and endpoints: Support for creation, deletion and querying of site 5G slice capabilities and endpoints (i.e., support for dynamic 5G slice allocation, support for dynamic UE attachment, Site 5G slice management endpoint)

2.8.2 Software diagram

In Figure 14 we depict the internal software architecture of this module. We highlight that this module has been completely released on this release of the platform. As depicted in the figure, this module is a spring-boot based Java application. The functionality implemented by each internal module is as follows:

- REST Controller: Implements the REST server which receives the creation, deletion, and query requests for the different VITAL-5G site records, enforcing the access control mechanisms through the access control client. The source code of this component is located in the *it.nextworks.inventory.nbi* package inside the multi-site-inventory project.
- Inventory Service: Performs in-depth validation of the creation, deletion, and querying requests, and performs the operation interacting with the modules database by means of the JPA-based repositories. The source code for this module is located in the *it.nextworks.inventory.services* of the multi-site-inventory project.
- JPA-based repositories: Mediate between the database and the internal modules, hiding the database management and querying complexity. The source code for this module is located in the *it.nextworks.inventory.repos* of the multi-site-inventory project.

Figure 14: Multi-site inventory internal software architecture

2.8.3 API and interfaces

In Figure 15 we depict the API of the module, which is fully available in OpenAPI format²¹.

VITAL-5G multi-site inventory 1.0.0 OAS3

- Device Management and Querying ∨
- Monitoring Information Management and Querying ∨
- 5G Slicing Information Management and Querying ∨
- NFVO Information Management and Querying ∧

GET	<code>/{testbed}/nfvos/{nfvoId}</code>	Get a Nfvo	∨
PUT	<code>/{testbed}/nfvos/{nfvoId}</code>	Update a Nfvo	∨
DELETE	<code>/{testbed}/nfvos/{nfvoId}</code>	Delete a Nfvo	∨
GET	<code>/{testbed}/nfvos</code>	List All Nfvos	∨
POST	<code>/{testbed}/nfvos</code>	Create a Nfvo	∨

Figure 15: Multi-site inventory API

²¹ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/multi-site-inventory/API/

2.8.4 Baseline software updates

This module has been developed completely within VITAL-5G.

2.8.5 Software assets

2.8.5.1 Repositories / Images

This module is released under an Apache 2 license, and the source code is available in the project GitLab repository²².

The code is divided mainly divided in two maven projects:

- *Multi-site-interfaces*: This project contains the Java classes implementing the interfaces and the information elements used to interact with this module. It is mean to be used as a dependency by other Java based modules interacting with this module (i.e., Service LCM, NetApps, Services and Experiment Catalogue).
- *Multi-site-inventory*: This contains the logic of the sub-modules, as detailed previously. It uses the *Multi-site-interfaces* as a dependency, implements the interfaces and uses the information elements of this latter project.

2.8.5.2 Installation

The install folder in the module repository²³ contains the installation instructions and docker files which allow to build and execute this module using Docker.

2.9 Monitoring Platform

The VITAL-5G centralized monitoring platform is responsible for: i) the collection of different types of metrics/KPIs coming from the three 5G testbeds, i.e., their local monitoring systems, and ii) the exposure of collected metrics to the other VITAL-5G platform components (e.g., AI-based diagnostics, or Result-based analytics). This monitoring platform interfaces with the local monitoring systems deployed on each of the three testbeds, and it collects either real-time or bulk metrics that those local systems measure and monitor. Such a centralized monitoring platform facilitates the execution and monitoring of the ongoing experiments, as it enables diagnostic elements to detect anomalies and changes in service and network quality, and to correspondingly act upon those detected events. The software solution is designed and developed as a Java Spring Boot application with ZeroMQ pub/sub system.

2.9.1 First-full-release features

For the first full release of this software module, various features have been enabled, and these features are also the result of several integration activities with the other VITAL-5G platform components and local monitoring systems on each of the testbeds. The list below provides an overview of the main features that have been designed and developed so far.

- **Dynamic creation of monitoring topics**: After a vertical service is created via VITAL-5G platform, as a part of an ongoing experiment, the monitoring system needs to be triggered to create particular topics that will be used by a corresponding local testbed to report the measurements. Thus, based on the request coming from the Service LCM (as illustrated in the workflow Figure 16, steps 1-2), the VITAL-5G centralized monitoring platform starts the dynamic creation of the topic. The topic is created based on the type of metric that needs to be collected, also stating the source of metric (i.e., local testbed such as BE, RO, or GR testbed). The communication between Service LCM and centralized monitoring platform is REST-based.

²² https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/multi-site-inventory

²³ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_platform/multi-site-inventory/-/tree/main/install

- **Real-time collection of metrics from the 5G testbeds:** As soon as a particular topic is created upon the trigger from the Service LCM, VITAL-5G centralized monitoring platform dynamically informs the corresponding 5G testbed, i.e., its local monitoring system, about the type of metric it needs to start publishing towards the centralized monitoring system (Figure 16, steps 3-4). The local monitoring systems installed on the 5G testbeds are fully responsible for measuring the KPIs from their underlying infrastructure, network, and services. When it comes to topic configuration on the testbeds, the communication between local monitoring system on the testbeds and centralized monitoring system on the VITAL-5G platform is REST-based. However, for the purpose of collecting metrics, i.e., publishing metrics to the centralized monitoring platform, each 5G testbed is using a ZeroMQ publisher.
- **Dynamic exposure of collected metrics towards external entities:** All metrics received on the centralized monitoring system are made available on the internal ZeroMQ publisher of the centralized monitoring system. Thus, components such as the Results Analytics and AI-based diagnostics can subscribe to it to collect the metrics to perform analysis and anomaly detection, thereby leveraging the developed ZeroMQ subscriber (Figure 16, steps 5-9). It is important to note that the collected data is not accessible only by those two components, but by any external entity interested in collecting metrics from the testbeds.
- **Dynamic visualization of the collected metrics:** The visualization of all metrics collected from various 5G testbeds, i.e., their local monitoring systems, is performed through a dynamic creation of Grafana dashboards and panels (Figure 16, step 4.2). For each collected metric, a new panel on the Grafana dashboard is created (stating the type of metric, and originating testbed), thereby facilitating the view and monitoring of KPI fluctuations.
- **Dynamic termination of data collection process:** When the experiment is finished, and thus the vertical service needs to be terminated, the collection of data related to this service will be also completed. In particular, Service LCM sends a REST-based termination request towards centralized monitoring platform, which stops all active subscribers and removes all Grafana dashboards. For that purpose, i.e., to prevent the existence of topics that are not used anymore, the centralized monitoring platform informs the local monitoring system on the corresponding testbed that service is terminated, and no further metrics are required. The data collection is dynamically terminated, but the data that has been previously collected for this particular service and experiment will be stored on the centralized monitoring platform as a historical type of data, and as such it can be used for debugging or ML model training purposes.

Figure 16: Monitoring workflow.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No 101016567

2.9.2 Software diagram

The software diagram of the VITAL-5G centralized monitoring platform is presented in Figure 17. It illustrates the internal software components, such as Data Collection Manager (DCM) and Data Storage Manager (DSM), as well as the interaction with the external components (local monitoring systems and subscribing components such as Results Analytics and AI-based diagnostics) via defined integration interfaces.

Figure 17: Software architecture of the VITAL-5G centralized monitoring system s

In particular, the *Controller* within the DCM block is an agent responsible for managing the entire monitoring platform. It is responsible for the logic required for the REST-based communication between the centralized monitoring platform and: i) the Service LCM (all REST calls shown in Figure 19), ii) the local monitors on each testbed (all REST calls shown in Figure 20), and iii) the Data storage handler (all REST calls shown in Figure 21). The *Controller* agent makes sure that when the Service LCM makes a request for monitoring a particular type of metric, it dynamically generates a topic for that metric. This topic, along with the information provided by the Service LCM, is communicated to the corresponding local testbed and thus to its local monitor. The *Controller* sends a further request towards the other internal component, i.e., *Main ZMQ Broker*, to create a dynamic subscriber in order to retrieve the incoming metrics from the testbed(s). The *Controller* agent is also capable to dynamically generate a corresponding Grafana dashboard for that specific testbed, thereby creating a panel to visualize the metric.

The *Main ZMQ Broker* entity creates subscribers in a dynamic manner, in order to retrieve the KPIs from the local monitors on each of the testbeds. In total, this entity handles three types of active subscribers: i) subscriber for

the infrastructure KPIs, ii) subscriber for network KPIs, and iii) subscriber for service KPIs. The *Main ZMQ Broker* is also handling an internal publisher that is publishing all the received KPIs on the same topics as they are published from the local monitoring systems, in order to make those KPIs accessible for the other VITAL-5G platform components (e.g., Results Analytics, and AI-based diagnostics). Thus, all the aforementioned components are responsible for managing the collected data, as they are part of the DCM block.

Concerning the DSM block, The *Data storage handler* entity is responsible for storing all the received KPIs in a Postgres database. The *Dashboard handler* entity is an internal Grafana-based visualization handler. As shown in Figure 21, this entity exposes three types of REST requests: i) to create a Grafana dashboard, ii) to update a Grafana dashboard, and iii) to delete a Grafana dashboard. The *Controller* entity performs dynamic creation of Grafana panels for each of the KPIs that is collected from the 5G testbeds. This component also interacts with the VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI, thereby sharing the URL links to the newly created dashboards.

In total, there will be a maximum of three Grafana dashboards, i.e., Antwerp, Galati and Athens, corresponding to each of the 5G testbeds, as shown in Figure 18. In each of these dashboards, the metrics will be displayed in their specific panels. One example could be the end-to-end latency measured for the 5G testbed in Antwerp, and as such, this KPI will have its own panel within the Antwerp dashboard. Each of these dashboards is dynamically adjustable, which is extremely important for dynamic environments such as 5G ecosystems that are present in each of the pilot sites. In particular, if there are more metrics that need to be collected within the same experiment, the centralized monitoring platform is capable to dynamically adjust the topics, store the new data, and display it on a new Grafana panel. The same applies to the case of removing panels from the Grafana dashboard, which happens if there is no longer need to collect a certain type of metric from a particular 5G testbed.

Figure 18: Grafana dashboard showing collected metrics (Network latency and CPU load) from Antwerp, Galati, and Athens testbeds.

2.9.3 API and interfaces

As described in Sections 2.9.1 and 2.9.2, there are different integration activities that enabled successful interaction between the centralized monitoring platform and the other VITAL-5G platform components, including the local monitoring systems on each of the three testbeds. In this section, we briefly show the overview of the created interfaces.

In particular, Figure 19 illustrates the OpenAPI overview for the public interface of the VITAL-5G centralized monitoring platform. This API is used for communication between the monitoring system and the Service LCM (enabling the feature *Dynamic creation of monitoring topics*, as described in Section 2.9.1).

Service LCM ^

POST	/api/v1/platform/infrastructure	Create Infrastructure Metric	∨
POST	/api/v1/platform/service	Create Service Metric	∨
POST	/api/v1/platform/platform	Create Platform Metric	∨
DELETE	/api/v1/platform/shutdown	Reset the Vital-5G centralised monitoring platform	∨
DELETE	/api/v1/platform/infrastructure/{topic}	Delete a topic for an Infrastructure Metric	∨
DELETE	/api/v1/platform/service/{topic}	Delete a topic for an Service Metric	∨
DELETE	/api/v1/platform/platform/{topic}	Delete a topic for an Platform Metric	∨

Figure 19: OpenAPI for Public Interface of VITAL-5G centralized monitor.

Furthermore, Figure 20 illustrates the OpenAPI interfaces used for interaction between the VITAL-5G centralized monitoring platform and the local monitoring systems on each of the testbeds. This API is used for configuring the topics on the local monitors (enabling the feature *Real-time collection of metrics from the 5G testbeds*, as described in Section 2.9.1). Once the topics are configured, the rest of the communication between local monitoring systems and the centralized platform go through the ZeroMQ.

Interface/request to local monitor ^

POST	/localtestbed/antwerp	Requested to start the collection of a metric.	∨
POST	/localtestbed/galati	Requested to start the collection of a metric.	∨
POST	/localtestbed/Athens	Requested to start the collection of a metric.	∨
POST	/localTestbed/stop/metric/publisher	Requested to stop the collection of a metric.	∨

Figure 20: Interfaces from VITAL-5G centralized monitor to local testbed monitor.

In Figure 21, the internal API for communication between the internal centralized monitoring system components

Inter-centralised monitor ^

POST	/grafana/dashboard	Requested to create a Grafana Dashboard	∨
PUT	/grafana/dashboard/{dashboardId}	Requested to create a Grafana Dashboard	∨
DELETE	/grafana/dashboard/{deleteDashWithasboardId}	Requested to delete a Grafana Dashboard	∨

Figure 21: Internal API in VITAL-5G centralized monitor.

2.9.4 Baseline software updates

This software module is a newly developed component for the purpose of monitoring performance in all three trial sites, and as such, its design and development (including interfaces with the other modules) are fully performed within the confines of the VITAL-5G project.

2.9.5 Software assets

2.9.5.1 Repositories / Images

The VITAL-5G centralized monitoring platform is not open source. To make it easier to incorporate the local monitoring system of each testbed with the VITAL-5G monitor, Publisher and Subscriber agents are provided and

made available in the VITAL-5G Gitlab²⁴. The same level of support could be provided to the 3rd-party experimenters if there is an interest in publishing KPIs to the centralized monitoring platform, or for collecting metrics from different testbeds.

2.9.5.2 Software structure (open source)

This software component is not open source.

2.9.5.3 Installation

The installation folder in the module repository contains all the install instructions. This Spring based Java application is using Maven 3.8 to run, and it requires PostgreSQL 13 or higher, and Grafana v9 or higher. The current version of the VITAL-5G centralized monitoring platform is already deployed on a VM in the Orange testbed.

2.10 Results analytics

The Results Analysis component is responsible of consuming the information generated during a service's operation, analyse it, produce KPIs and provide insights regarding the observed performance and the validation of the requested conditions or SLAs. Additionally, it is capable of generating validation-based triggers to the Closed-loop control process for resizing/scaling networks slices and services. Except from its functional role, this component is also responsible for configuring and controlling the AI-based Diagnostics component, since its operation happens in parallel to the analysis and validation. The configuration information of the AI-based Diagnostics module is similar to the one used by Results Analytics but includes additional context regarding the NetApp, that is tested during the experiment, based on the initial configuration received by the LCM component. This additional context includes Network Service identifiers used to retrieve topology information for the elements taking part in the experiment. Information regarding the infrastructure and network resources used to deploy the NetApps may also be included.

2.10.1 First-full-release features

The Result analytics component was skipped from the first-full-release version to align with the release of the monitoring platform, so this will be the first release of this component. The features provided by this component, in the context of VITAL-5G, are:

- Metric collection and statistical analysis: the component is responsible to ingest the generated metrics collected, through the monitoring platform, and perform statistical analysis on them in order to provide a more detailed view of the achieved performance.
- KPI calculation and publishing: the component is also responsible to calculate simple or complex KPIs based on the provided formulas and make them available to the monitoring platform for further analysis.
- KPI validation: the validation of the calculated KPIs based on the pre-defined restrictions or SLAs is also supported.
- Report generation: finally, a report is generated containing all the information collected, calculated, and generated in a concise way in order to inform the experiment requester of the achieved performance and results.

An example of the generated report, regarding to a specific experiment is shown in Figure 22. In this experiment there is one test case with one service element, the server. The KPIs that are validated in this case are:

1. Server response time, calculated as the sum of the network latency and the server processing time

²⁴ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_platform/monitoring-platform

2. Average CPU load, calculated as the average of the CPU utilization of the server VM during service operations.

The results of the statistical analysis are shown along with the graphs for the performance of the KPI, in relation to the validation conditions set, as well as the correlation of the KPI values with the individual metrics used as input for the calculation.

Figure 22: Results Analysis report

2.10.2 Software diagram

The Result Analysis component is developed using Go, and as shown in Figure 23, it comprises of several submodules and external services, the descriptions of which are as follows:

- Management API: implements the REST server that is responsible for the LCM management of the component, the registration of new services to be monitored and the exposure of the generated results.
- Result Analysis & Validation Engine: handles the statistical analysis of the ingested metrics and the validation of the generated KPIs based on the provided conditions/SLAs.
- KPI Generation Engine: implements the logic behind the calculation of the requested KPIs based on the provided formulas and the metrics used as inputs.
- Management Database: acts as the state manager of the various services that are registered for monitoring on this component and is one of the sources of data that will be included in the report.
- Metric Database: acts as the collected metric storage to be used in the KPI calculation as well as the actual generated KPIs and is one of the sources of data that will be included in the report.
- Report Generator: handle the generation and exposure of the final report.

Figure 23: Result Analysis component internal software architecture

2.10.3 API and interfaces

The RA component requires external interfaces for management purposes and exposing the generated results. One of its interactions, with the Monitoring platform, utilizes ZeroMQ subscribers and publishers to ingest and publish metrics and KPIs respectively. Another external interaction is also the interface between the GUI and Report generation exposed endpoint in order to make the generated report available to the platform users. Finally, the lifecycle management of the RAV component, and its typical workflow, is managed externally by the LCM component. Additionally, the RA component is responsible to manage the LCM operation of the AI Diagnostic component. This is achieved by transforming the configuration and actions it receives from the LCM component and propagating them to the AI Diagnostic component. This interaction is done by design in order to guarantee the all the necessary inputs for the diagnostic process.

To accomplish the aforementioned interactions, a northbound API is provided, shown in Figure 24. The OpenAPI documentation is also provided in the project's platform repository²⁵

²⁵ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_platform/results-analytics/-/tree/main/

Figure 24: Result Analytics API

The provided northbound API will be further extended in order to support the integration with the closed-loop control mechanisms planned for the next drop of the platform.

2.10.4 Baseline software updates

The RA module was originally created during the 5G-EVE project for the same purposes used in VITAL-5G, result analytics, KPI calculation and validation. In 5G-EVE, the notion of experiment was more prominent and as such all operations happened before and after the experiment. This is not the case for VITAL-5G. The updates and modifications to the software baseline are as follows:

- **[New Implementation]** One of the base differences between the two implementations, the 5G-EVE one and the one developed for VITAL-5G, is the real-time operation of the second one. Core parts of the component have been modified and the RA module is now capable of performing the required operations in parallel to service/experiment running.
- **[New Implementation]** In 5G-EVE a Kafka broker was used to transport the required messages across the components. In VITAL-5G ZeroMQ is selected as the transport mechanism for these messages. As such, suitable ZMQ subscribers and publishers have been developed and integrated into the component. These will allow the message exchange between the RA component and the centralized Monitoring platform for metrics ingestion and KPI publishing.
- **[New Implementation]** The RA component has been extended with a mechanism to generate threshold triggered events based on the results of the KPI validation. The purpose of this mechanism is to propagate these validation-based events, when the requested KPIs failed their validation, to the LCM's closed-loop control mechanism of the need to resize/scale the provided resources.

2.10.5 Software assets

2.10.5.1 Repositories / Images

This module is proprietary, and as such is released in binary format, which is available in the project's Gitlab repository²⁶

²⁶ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_platform/results-analytics/-/tree/main/

2.10.5.2 Software structure

As the component is proprietary, not a lot of detail can be provided. An abstract view of the internal software architecture can be deduced from the software diagram provided above.

2.10.5.3 Installation

The install folder in the component repository²⁷ contains the installation instructions and docker files which are needed to execute this module using Docker. Two supporting services are also included in the compose file, a MongoDB container to handle the role of the Management DB and a PostgreSQL container to handle the role of the Metrics DB.

2.11 AI-based Diagnostic

The AI-based Diagnostics component consumes information regarding to a service's performance, during an experiment, and after analysing that information, produces insights on the observed performance of the various elements that comprise the service. In order to perform the required operations, the diagnostic process utilizes as input the generated metrics and KPIs collected from the execution of similar experiments of the same service, along with the service topology and resources information regarding the specific service. Experiments are considered similar when they include the same metrics and KPIs and as such will generate the same number of features for the AI models. This information is used, at first as the training data set for the AI models generated per NetApp, and afterwards, provided that a sufficient training data set of the models has been achieved, it is used as input data for the inference stage of the same models. The diagnostic component is also responsible for detecting anomalies in the behaviour of the various elements as well as identifying possible root causes of detected problems or performance degradations during the experiment. After the detection of such anomalies and performance degradations, it also triggers diagnostic events to the Closed-loop control process in order to suggest the necessary actions to alleviate these issues. To accomplish that, various AI algorithms has been implemented as modules to be used as part of the Anomaly detection and the Root Cause Analysis mechanisms. Such algorithms are Self Organized Maps (SOM) and DBSCAN clustering as well as custom algorithms for topological investigation, correlation, and root cause analysis.

2.11.1 First-full-release features

The AI Diagnostic component was not included in the first-full-release version to align with the release of the monitoring platform, needed for its integration. This will be the first release of this component. The features provided by this component, in the context of VITAL-5G, are:

- Anomaly detection: the component is responsible for utilizing AI clustering algorithms in order to detect any anomalies or performance degradations based on the perceived performance, as demonstrated using the collected metrics and KPIs
- Root Cause Analysis: the diagnostic component, upon detection of an anomaly, utilizes the available information (metrics, KPIs, their categories and the hierarchy of the deployment architecture) and a reasoning system, produces insights as to the cause of the detected anomaly and possibly the perceived performance degradation. Depending on the results of this process, the component has the capability to offer suggestions for alleviating this degradation, by suggesting countermeasure like scaling of service components etc...

An example of the generated report based on the results of the AI diagnostic process is shown in Figure 25 and Figure 26. In this experiment there is one test case with one service element, the server. The collected metrics and KPIs are vectorized, correlated spatiotemporally, and passed to the AI algorithms module for analysis. The results of this analysis can be seen on the report. An interactive heatmap is provided for examination per vector,

²⁷ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_platform/results-analytics/-/tree/main/

regarding the status of the service and the performance of each node. When an anomaly is detected, additional information can be retrieved, when available, regarding the cause of this anomaly, either as the result of the Root cause analysis, or as statistical information regarding the performance observed.

Figure 25: AI Diagnostic anomaly detection report

Figure 26: AI Diagnostic vector statistics report

2.11.2 Software diagram

The AI Diagnostic component is developed using Go and Python, for the AI algorithms module, and as shown in Figure 27, it comprises several submodules and external services, the descriptions of which are as follows:

- Management API: implements the REST server that is responsible for the LCM management of the component, the registration of new services to be monitored and the exposure of the diagnosis results.
- Vectorizer: handles the ingestion of the collected metrics and KPIs, their spatiotemporal correlation and their organization into vectors suitable to be consumed by the AI algorithms.
- AI Algorithms module: implements the various AI algorithms used in the diagnostic process for anomaly detection and root cause analysis.
- Management database: acts as the state manager of the various services that are registered for monitoring on this component and is one of the sources of data that will be included in the report.
- Metric database: acts as the storage of the raw and analysed vectors to be used in the diagnostic process and is one of the sources of data that will be included in the report.

Figure 27: AI Diagnostic component internal software architecture

2.11.3 API and interfaces

The AI Diagnostic component requires external interfaces for management purposes and exposing the generated insights regarding the observed performance and detected issues. One of its interactions, with the Monitoring platform, utilizes ZeroMQ subscribers to ingest metrics and KPIs. Another necessary interaction is with a component that handles its lifecycle management. In this platform, the component responsible to do that is the RA component.

To accomplish these interactions, a northbound API is provided, shown in Figure 28. The OpenAPI documentation is also provided in the project’s platform repository²⁸

²⁸ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_platform/ai-based-diagnostics/-/tree/main/install

PD API 1.0.0-oas3 OAS3

doc/apis/PerformanceDiagnosis_OpenAPI.yaml

Performance Diagnosis API

developers Operations available to regular developers ^

GET	/health	retrieves the health status of the service	▼
GET	/listServices	list all the registered services	▼
GET	/listMetrics	list all the registered metrics	▼
POST	/fetchValues	fetch the requested last values of the selected metrics	▼
GET	/fetchVectors/{serviceID}/{selection}/{number}	retrieved the selected number of latest vectors of a registered service	▼
GET	/removeService/{serviceID}	remove a service from the registered services list	▼
GET	/selectService/{serviceID}/view	retrieved the information of a registered service	▼
GET	/selectService/{serviceID}/metricTables	retrieved the metric tables names for a specified service	▼
GET	/selectService/{serviceID}/topology	retrieved the topology for a specified service	▼

Figure 28: AI Diagnostic API

The provided northbound API will be further extended in order to support the integration with the closed-loop control mechanisms planned for the next drop of the platform.

2.11.4 Baseline software updates

The AI diagnostic module was originally created during the 5G-EVE project for the same purposes used in VITAL-5G, to provide performance diagnosis of an experiment and provide insights on the observed performance. In 5G-EVE, the workflows were focused on an experiment, and as such all operations happened before and after the experiment.

- **[New Implementation]** One of the base differences between the two implementations, the 5G-EVE one and the one developed for VITAL-5G, is the real-time operation of the second one. Core parts of the component have been modified and the AI Diagnostic module is now capable of performing the required operations in parallel to service/experiment running.
- **[New Implementation]** In 5G-EVE a Kafka broker was used to transport the required messages across the components. In VITAL-5G ZeroMQ is selected as the transport mechanism for these messages. As such, suitable ZMQ subscribers and publishers have been developed and integrated into the component. These will allow the metric and KPI ingestion from the Monitoring platform to the AI Diagnostic component.
- **[New Implementation]** The AI Diagnostic component has been extended with a mechanism to generate diagnostic triggered events based on the results of the AI model inference operations. The purpose of this mechanism is to propagate these diagnostic events, when an anomaly or performance degradation is detected along with information regarding the cause/origin of this event, to the LCM's closed-loop control mechanism. This information can, subsequently, be used to trigger resizing/scaling actions regarding the provided resources.

2.11.5 Software assets

2.11.5.1 Repositories / Images

This module is proprietary, and as such is released in binary format, which is available in the project's Gitlab repository²⁹.

2.11.5.2 Software structure

As the component is proprietary, not a lot of detail can be provided. An abstract view of the internal software architecture can be deduced from the software diagram provided above.

2.11.5.3 Installation

The install folder in the component repository³⁰ contains the installation instructions and docker files which are needed to execute this module using Docker. Two supporting services are also included in the compose file, a MongoDB container to handle the role of the Management DB and a PostgreSQL container to handle the role of the Metrics DB.

²⁹ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_platform/ai-based-diagnostics/-/tree/main/install

³⁰ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_platform/ai-based-diagnostics/-/tree/main/install

3 VITAL-5G NetApps

In D2.2, the early versions of the NetApps included two different vertical-agnostic (VA), and two vertical-specific (VS) NetApps which were used to implement services across the three use cases of the project. In this first-full release version of the VITAL-5G NetApps, most of the functionalities are enabled for supporting services for the 3 Use Cases of the project, namely:

- **Data collection from vessels (UC1 and UC2).** This release includes real-time data collection and data publishers for other NetApps to subscribe and collect data from vessels as well as public interfaces to other 3rd parties. (VS8, VS9)
- **Data ingestion, fusion processing, and organization (all UCs).** In this release, enhanced functionalities related to data manipulation, data fusion and persistence are offered. Decision support functionalities and services offered to other NetApps are also available. (VA1, VA2, VA6)
- **Navigation-related functionalities for vessels (UC1).** The release enables different functionalities for enabling network-assisted navigation for vessels such as: real-time location of the vessel, geodata reception, planning data, optimal navigation speed, real-time digital twin of a vessel (VA5, VS5, VS6, VS7)
- **Basic robot-related functionalities (UC3).** This release enables data ingestion for IoT, custom actions, events and alerts, computational offloading for human-robot collaboration and task allocation and planning for logistics management. (VA4, VS1, VS2)
- **AI-related functionalities (All UCs).** This release enables ingestion of vessel data from a distributed filesystem and ML-related functionalities (supervised learning) for remote inspection and risk assessment in a vessel (VA3)

As the testbeds and experimentation platform have evolved and are at their first full versions, so are most of the NetApps targeted to be developed. Only VS3 and VS4 will be released with the 3rd release of the NetApps, since the focus on this release has been set on the data ingestion functionality provided by VA4. In Table 9 we summarize the features introduced by each NetApp on each release.

Table 9 NetApp first full version functionalities

NetApp Code	NetApp Name	List of Features
VA1	Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & automation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IoT controller for the two-way interaction with IoT devices • MQTT/HTTP Gateway enabling the communication between off-site and on-site infrastructure • Rule engine for Decision support • Persistence service providing persistence and caching services to all other NetApp components
VA2	Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & post processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other functionalities related to data manipulation, fusion, and persistence • Supervised machine learning (ML)-related functionalities
VA3	Remote inspection & risk assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ML-related functionalities for remote inspection and risk assessment. • Outlier detections algorithms. • Ingestion of vessel engine data information from a distributed filesystem

VA4	IoT Management Platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management of Data Buses for Data Injection: • Management and triggering of custom actions for alert and event. • Customized dashboards configuration and visualization
VA5	Real time digital twin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LiDAR fusion • LiDAR data filtering • Create an obstacle map of the environment of the vessel.
VA6	Data stream organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supports organization of data according to payload content • Supports receiving data via Pub/Sub paradigms • Supports custom processing functions (for organizing streams)
VS1	Indoor robot navigation & coordination with task planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logistics Lifecycle Management Service (Logistics LCM). • AGV Task Allocation and Planning.
VS2	Human-robot collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HMI assist. • Computational offloading
VS5	Remote Vessel Monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Camera view of the vessel • Real-time location of the vessel on an interactive 3D map • A view that shows the result of VS7 on the dashboard and allows for the user of the dashboard to interact with VS7
VS6	Assisted vessel navigation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determines a path to the destination (global planning) • Finds an optimized local path (local planning)
VS7	Navigation speed optimizer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fully tested and integrated with VS8 to receive the geodata • Fully tested and integrated with VS5 to receive the planning data and provide the calculated optimal navigation speed • API traffic encrypted with Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) certificates. • Open Authorization (OAuth) v2 used for authentication,

VS8	On board data collection & interfacing for vessel Tercofin II	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Final real-time data collection from the vessel Tercofin II • Data Proxy Server with Subscriber defined for data collection from vessel • Data Publisher for other NetApps to subscribe and collect data retrieved from the vessel • Data manager & Data storage, and Public interface that exposes data either through a REST API, or through a pub/sub mechanism (subscribers running in other NetApps)
VS9	On board data collection & interfacing for NAVROM vessel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supports data collected from vessel: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Depth sensor data ○ AIS data ○ Engine data ○ Air quality data ○ Water quality data ○ Video stream data

Table 10 NetApp first full version partners involvement, delivery method, and license

NetApp Code	Partners involved	Delivery (Software image/Package/repository) method	License
VA1	WINGS	Offered as Virtual Machine image at https://share.wings-ict-solutions.eu/vital5g/	Software keys and guidance are provided to partners for onboarding the VM in the VITAL-5G platform.
VA2	BEIA+INCE	Relevant components will be provided as Docker images. Access to dockers will be granted to 3 rd parties upon request, along with relevant guidance/ support for onboarding.	Closed source, guidelines to be provided upon request
VA3	INCE	Relevant components will be provided as Docker images. Access to dockers will be granted to 3 rd parties upon request, along with relevant guidance/ support for onboarding.	Closed source, guidelines to be provided upon request
VA4	NXW	Available as a set of VM snapshots (qcow2 format) through the following FTP: Server: mercurio.nextworks.it Port: 9292	Software keys and guidance are provided to partners for onboarding the

		<p>Files:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rest Controller: Vital5G_VA4_Rest_Controller.qcow2 • IoT Supervisor: Vital5G_VA4_Rest_Controller.qcow2 • Message Broker: Vital5G_VA4_Rest_Controller.qcow2 • IoT alarm & event manager: Vital5G_VA4_Rest_Controller.qcow2 • Datastore & Dashboard: Vital5G_VA4_Datastore_Dashboard.qcow2 	VM in the VITAL-5G platform.
VA5	IMEC	<p>Docker repository:</p> <p>https://hub.docker.com/repository/docker/ovasseur/vital5g-va5</p>	Access to VA5 will be granted to collaborators added to the Dockerhub repository.
VA6	BEIA	<p>Source code: https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_netapps/data-stream-organization</p>	GPLv3
VS1	WINGS	<p>Offered as Virtual Machine image at https://share.wings-ict-solutions.eu/vital5g/</p>	Software keys and guidance are provided to partners for onboarding the VM in the VITAL-5G platform.
VS2	WINGS	<p>Offered as Virtual Machine image at https://share.wings-ict-solutions.eu/vital5g/</p>	Software keys and guidance are provided to partners for onboarding the VM in the VITAL-5G platform.
VS5	IMEC+SF	<p>Docker image is available for on-premise deployment. Link is not public.</p>	Access to VS5 is granted to IMEC to host on their premises
VS6	IMEC	<p>Docker repository</p> <p>https://gitlab.ilabt.imec.be:4567/vital-5g/vs6</p>	Access to VS6 will be granted to collaborators added to the

			Dockerhub repository.
VS7	DT	Available as a Docker image: https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_netapps/vs7	GPLv3
VS8	IMEC	<p>Docker repository: https://hub.docker.com/repository/docker/ninask92/vital-5g,</p> <p>Docker image: https://hub.docker.com/layers/195383878/ninask92/vital-5g/vs8/images/sha256-6dd9756c9ef37a2582cde2de787babe41629394f5eaf63beddedbb984326a743?context=repo</p> <p>API specification: https://app.swaggerhub.com/apis/imec-vital-5g/VS8/1.0.0</p>	Access to VS8 will be granted to collaborators added to the Dockerhub repository
VS9	BEIA	Source code : https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_netapps/data-collection-navrom	GPLv3

3.1 VA1 Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & automation

The VA1 NetApp with title “Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion and automation” is responsible for data ingestion and two-way communication with on-site equipment, decision support using rules and inference, device monitoring and field assistance.

VA1 has been documented in deliverable D2.2 as part of the early-drop releases. Internal components and services have been enhanced and improved but the interfaces remain identical the same as described in D2.2, therefore please refer to this deliverable.

A common question may be what the difference between VA1 and VA2 NetApps is; the answer is that since the VA1 NetApp is proprietary software it cannot be merged with other NetApps with similar naming and functionality (VA2). VA1 is utilized in Use Case 3: “Automation and Remote operation of freight Logistics”.

3.1.1 Release features

See D2.2

3.1.2 Functional blocks

See D2.2

3.1.3 API and interfaces

See D2.2

3.1.4 Deployment (IoT devices & 5G slices)

See D2.2

3.1.5 Baseline software updates

The VA1 NetApp does not share any code or features with previous projects such as 5G-EVE. It is part of the WINGS Chariot platform developed by WINGS ICT Solutions and is covered by a proprietary license which allows usage within the scope of VITAL-5G, both by the VITAL-5G partners and 3rd-party experimenters.

3.1.6 Software assets

3.1.6.1 Repositories / Images

The VA1 NetApp is offered as Virtual Machine image at <https://share.wings-ict-solutions.eu/vital5g/>. Software keys and guidance are provided to partners for onboarding the VM in the VITAL-5G platform.

3.2 VA2 Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & post-processing

3.2.1 Release features

In deliverable 2.2 [2], an early-drop version of this NetApp was described. Specifically, it focused on the data collection and persistence of the incoming sensor data. In this early drop version, example scripts for ingesting data from an InfluxDB database³¹ to a distributed filesystem which will allow for storage (i.e., Apache HDFS³² storage layer coupled with Apache Hive³³ - an SQL tabular data storage layer - and Trino³⁴ an open source distributed query engine). Data ingested were provided using a data generator to populate the InfluxDB database.

In this release, the focus is shifted to other functionalities related to data manipulation, fusion and persistence and the supervised machine learning (ML)-related functionalities (see also the relevant description in Section 2.2.2). Lastly, a dedicated user interface (UI) is included so as to allow users to use VA2 and visualize results easily.

3.2.2 Functional blocks

A description of the various functional blocks of VA2 was provided in D2.1 [1]. More specifically, the main functionalities supported are:

- **Data Collection:** Responsible for the collection of data through the southbound interfacing with the testbed(s) and/or external sources and NetApps.
- **Data Fusion:** Performs the logical transformation of data to be further utilized by other VITAL-5G components or NetApps. In more detail, it also allows for the spatiotemporal correlation of the received information for the logical fusion of data and applies transformations and manipulations necessary.
- **ML module:** It is comprised of the Unsupervised and Supervised Modelling submodules, the Autotune Engine, and the ML Registry. It incorporates mechanisms that ensure the optimal ML model will be used for advanced analytics depending on the application. In this case, the forecasting/ supervising approaches are explored as they are more relevant to VA2 NetApp-related applications. The Autotune Engine ensures the optimal hyper-parameter tuning for multiple modelling approaches and the best are stored in the ML registry. The results of these approaches can then be stored in a persistence layer.
- **Data Persistence:** This component refers to a distributed data lake allowing for storage of both structured and unstructured data. It is where the raw data/KPIs, as well as their transformations (e.g., imputed datasets, fused data) and the ML modelling results are persisted. It is also responsible for exposing data through the appropriate APIs to the dashboard, other components and 3rd party NetApps.

³¹ <https://docs.influxdata.com/influxdb>

³² <https://hadoop.apache.org/>

³³ <https://hive.apache.org/>

³⁴ <https://trino.io/>

Based on the aforementioned functionalities, VA2’s software architecture is presented in Figure 29.

Figure 29: VA2 software architecture.

In short, sensor data are ingested through the appropriate interfaces (Influx-Hive connector) and stored (note that this aspect is not included in this release). Apache Airflow³⁵ assists in the data operations pipelines to allow for the data spatiotemporal fusion, imputation -where needed- and specific transformations of data before ML models can be employed. The Autotune Engine allows for an automated selection of the best ML model through a hyperparameter tuning process, while all training metrics and model artifacts are logged in MLflow³⁶. It should be noted that although not originally included in the NetApp architecture and was not part of VA2, a UI/dashboard has also been developed as an added component that can exploit the VA2 mechanisms and visualize results. It presents vessel trajectory-related results, but also includes a form where 3rd party users can train their own models by choosing from the models and respective hyperparameters available and specifying the ingested data used for model development. At the same time, they can also monitor through an MLflow-specific view the various ML results and compare their performance (see also Figure 31).

³⁵ <https://airflow.apache.org/>

³⁶ <https://mlflow.org/>

Figure 30: VA2 UI - Indicative views for trajectory and model training.

Figure 31: MLflow view for VA2 model training results.

3.2.3 AI/ML methodology

In this release, two types of forecasting modelling approaches are supported, namely:

- Seasonal Auto-Regressive Integrated Moving Average with eXogenous factors (SARIMAX) model using the Statsmodels library³⁷. It is the extension of the ARIMA modeling that includes only an autoregressive

³⁷ <https://www.statsmodels.org>

term (AR) and a moving-average (MA) term. SARIMAX supports both seasonality in the dataset and in addition to this has the capability to handle exogenous variables.

- Prophet³⁸: An automatic forecasting procedure for time series data based on an additive model where non-linear trends are fit with seasonality and other effects (e.g. holidays).

Both models can be applied to specified time-series data already ingested in the persistence entity (generic forecasting). For the case of trajectory prediction however, a case-specific implementation is offered that includes a pre-processing and post-processing step (Delta Angle Transformation) for trajectory calculation/prediction.

For the automated training of the models, a hyperparameter tuning process based on grid search for a selected KPI is performed.

3.2.4 API and interfaces

In this section, a detailed description for the APIs developed under the FastAPI framework³⁹ follows. The latter is based on (and is fully compatible with) the OpenAPI specification. These APIs are split as: (a) public, i.e. available to 3rd parties; and (b) private, meaning that the relevant APIs are indirectly accessible to 3rd parties only through the NetApp UI.

3.2.4.1 Public

POST `api/predict-trajectory`

Description: This service is specific to vessel trajectory prediction. It accepts a selected forecasting model along with a preferred range of hyperparameters. It then performs hyperparameter optimization based on a grid-search. The best hyperparameters for each model are selected, while all training metrics and model artifacts are logged in MLFlow. Currently, it supports two types of forecasting models, namely SARIMAX, Prophet, but it can be easily extended to include more.

Usage: Accepts a selection of latitude, longitude and timestamp filters to extract data from, the vessel ID of which the trajectory will be predicted, a selected model and its hyperparameter search space.

Returns: Metrics, model hyperparameters and status of the best performing model.

POST `api/generic/train`

Description: This service performs generic forecasting on selected input data, i.e. the timeseries data ingested into the HDFS system through other NetApps (see also details in VS9 description for AIS, engine, environmental sensor and depth sensor data). It accepts a selected forecasting model along with a preferred range of model hyperparameters, for instance “Order P” for the ARIMA modelling approach. As in the previous case, the best hyperparameters for each model are selected, while all training metrics and model artifacts are logged in MLFlow. Currently, it supports two types of forecasting models, namely SARIMAX, Prophet, but it can be easily extended to include more.

Usage: Accepts a selection of database filters to extract the input from, the target value upon which the predictions will be made, a selected model and its hyperparameter search space.

Returns: Metrics, model hyperparameters and status of the best performing model.

GET `api/forecast`

Description: This service performs forecasting for a specified number of steps on a trained trajectory prediction model.

³⁸ <https://github.com/facebook/prophet>

³⁹ <https://fastapi.tiangolo.com/>

Usage: Accepts the name of the experiment that contains the trained trajectory model and the number of steps to be predicted.

Returns: A list of the historic coordinates (translated into latitude and longitude) and the predicted coordinates of a specific vessel, including their respective confidence levels and deviations from the mean.

GET `api/generic/forecast`

Description: This service performs forecasting for a specified number of steps on a trained generic model.

Usage: Accepts the name of the experiment that contains the trained generic model and the number of steps to be predicted.

Returns: The predicted values, including their respective confidence levels and deviations from the mean.

GET `api/fetch-results`

Description: This service provides a list of all the training experiments that have been completed, including metrics and details for each run.

Usage: Accepts the experiment group (i.e. vessel trajectory or generic experiments) to fetch results from.

Returns: A list of the experiments and train specific details.

DELETE `experiments/delete`

Description: This route accepts an experiment name and deletes it from the MLFlow database.

Usage: Accepts an experiment id to be deleted

Returns: A successful message that the experiment has been deleted

3.2.4.2 *Internal*

GET `api/model-options`

Description: This service returns a list of all available data that can be used as parameters for training the vessel trajectory prediction models.

Usage: No request parameters required.

Returns: Available models and hyperparameters, KPI metrics and vessel IDs.

GET `/api/generic/form-options`

Description: This service returns a list of all available data that can be used as parameters for the generic forecasting models.

Usage: No request parameters required.

Returns: Available models and hyperparameters, KPI metrics and the available database schemas, tables and columns to select data from.

GET `/api/historic-trajectory`

Description: This service provides a list of the historic coordinates for a specified vessel.

Usage: Accepts the MMSI of the selected vessel and the timeframe to draw data from.

Returns: List of historic latitude and longitude of a selected vessel converted into a GeoJSON⁴⁰ format.

3.2.5 Deployment (IoT devices & 5G slices)

While for the case of forecasting future trajectories the selected data used are the vessel's position, supplied by the ingested AIS sensor data, this NetApp also allows for data fusion of information coming from different sensors to be persisted in Apache HDFS and further utilized either by the NetApp's generic forecasting models or by other NetApps/ 3rd parties. More specifically, the current release allows for the spatiotemporal fusion AIS data, environmental measurements, vessel engine sensor and depth sensor data.

3.2.6 Baseline software updates

In this release, the focus is shifted to other functionalities related to data fusion and persistence, and the supervised ML-related functionalities (see also the relevant description in section 3.2.3). Lastly, a dedicated UI is included so as to allow users to use VA2 and visualize results easily.

3.2.7 Software assets

3.2.7.1 Repositories / Images

The early drop release was under an AGPLv3 licence. However, the current ML-related and data fusion scheme work is proprietary, and the relevant components will be provided as Docker images.

Through the delivered UI and APIs to 3rd parties, users will be given the opportunity to run various ML-models, acquiring results as well as details on model type, hyperparameters and model performance during the training stage.

3.2.7.2 Software structure (open source)

This release will be closed source

3.3 VA3 Remote inspection & risk assessment

3.3.1 Release features

This is a first release of the VA3 NetApp. It supports the ML-related functionalities for remote inspection and risk assessment. This is done through the delivery of outlier detections algorithms. In this release, the NetApp is set to ingest vessel engine data information from a distributed filesystem. In this context, VA2 (see section 3.2) ingests the information which is then exploited in this NetApp.

However, the sensor data input and their source are subject to change in the next release to best support the functionality given.

3.3.2 Functional blocks

In deliverable D2.1 [1], the functional block architecture of VA3 was described. In more detail, though the appropriate interfaces the data are utilized for model training and inference and results are persisted in a data lake, then exposed to other components/ NetApps and 3rd party. As shown, the ML-module, described in section 3.2.2, is also utilized here, however in this case, the focus is on the unsupervised algorithmic approaches.

In fact, VA3 is designed with similar technologies and frameworks in mind as VA2 and its software component architecture is presented in the following figure:

⁴⁰ <https://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc7946>

Figure 32: VA3 software components.

VA3 assumes that data used for the related ML processes come either from a data lake/persistence component, or from interfacing with an external InfluxDB database/NetApp (the latter not implemented in this release). From then on, as in VA2, the ML engine allows for the training and deployment of the ML models. As opposed to VA2, in these cases the focus is on the outlier/anomaly detection approaches. The autotune engine allows for Bayesian hyperparameter optimization, selecting the best hyperparameters for each model and logs all training metrics and artifacts to MLflow.

While not originally included in the NetApp architecture and was not part of VA3, a UI/dashboard has also been developed (to be expanded in the future) as an added component that can exploit the VA3 mechanisms and visualize results. Currently, it includes a model training form for outlier detection methods (Figure 33). As in Figure 31, an MLflow-specific view allows 3rd party users monitor the various ML results and compare their performance.

Figure 33: VA3 UI – Indicative view

3.3.3 AI/ML methodology

In this release, the following two density-based clustering approaches are offered:

- Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN)
- Ordering Points To Identify the Clustering Structure (OPTICS)

Their purpose is to detect dense areas where data form clusters, while at the same time data points in sparse areas are considered outliers.

In addition to the above, One Class Support Vector Machine (SVM) is used also as an unsupervised model that learns the boundaries for the normal data points and therefore any points outside these boundaries are considered as outliers/anomalies.

The implementation is based on the Scikit-learn library⁴¹. The solution allows for Bayesian hyperparameter optimization, selecting the best hyperparameters for each model and logs all training metrics and artifacts to MLflow.

3.3.4 API and interfaces

A detailed description of the APIs developed under the FastAPI framework for this release follows. The latter is based on (and is fully compatible with) the OpenAPI specification

POST `api/train/automl`

Description: Accepts a list of selected outlier detection modelling approaches along with their preferred range of hyperparameters. It performs bayesian hyperparameter optimization, selecting the best hyperparameters for each model and logs all training metrics and artifacts to fMLFlow. Currently, the methods supported are DBSCAN, OPTICS, One Class SVM.

Usage: Accepts a selection of database filters to extract data from, followed by a list of models and their respective hyperparameter search space.

Returns: Metrics and parameters of the best performing models.

POST `api/predict/<mode>`

Description: Accepts a completed experiment name and performs outlier detection on a selected dataset. It supports 2 modes:

- load - for loading a pretrained saved model and inferring on the selected data;
- retrain - for retraining a model with the best performing hyperparameters of the experiment on the selected data.

Usage: Accepts a selection of database filters to extract data from and the experiment to load the models from.

Returns: A list of values classified either as normal (values > 0) or outliers (values = -1).

DELETE `experiments/delete`

Description: Accepts an experiment name and deletes it from the fMLFlow database.

Usage: Accepts an experiment ID to be deleted.

Returns: A successful message that the experiment has been deleted.

⁴¹ <https://scikit-learn.org/>

3.3.5 Deployment (IoT devices & 5G slices)

In this early release, VA3 exploits the use of vessel engine data in order to detect irregular/ outlying behaviour patterns and work as an early warning mechanism.

3.3.6 Baseline software updates

This is the first time these components are released. There are based on Incelligent's IP and work carried out in this project's duration.

3.3.7 Software assets

3.3.7.1 Repositories / Images

VA3 is proprietary and the relevant components will be provided either as Docker images.

However, through the delivered UI and APIs for 3rd party exploitation, users will be given the opportunity to run various ML-models, acquiring results as well as details on model type, hyperparameters and model performance during the training stage.

3.4 VA4 IoT Management platform

In D2.1 [1], we provided an early-stage description of the NetApp in terms of: (i) Functional blocks and interfaces of this NetApp; (ii) Targeted deployment scenarios. In this document we build upon these early-stage description documenting the evolution of the functional blocks and interfaces implemented in the first release of this NetApp, and detailing the deployment scenarios.

3.4.1 Release features

In this first release of the NetApp, The IoT Management Platform NetApp implements a complete tool to collect, store, visualize and analyse a continuous flow of data exposed by IoT systems. In particular, this release supports the following features:

- Management of Data Buses for Data Injection:
- Management and triggering of custom actions for alert and event.
- Customized dashboards configuration and visualization

3.4.2 Functional blocks

Figure 34: VA4 Functional blocks and Interfaces

The IoT Management Platform is composed by a set of internal blocks, depicted in Figure 34, that implement all the main functionalities and three interfaces that securely ensure the configuration and communication with external modules. More in details, the first release includes of the NetApp the following internal blocks:

- **Rest Controller:** The component responsible to expose a unified REST Interface to configure and retrieve information from the other internal blocks of the NetApp. More in detail, the most important configuration tasks that the Rest Controller can address are:
 - Manage Buses or Objects of the IoT Supervisor to enable the data retrieval from a data source
 - Manage Datastore and Dashboard module to enable the storing and visualization of the data coming from the IoT Supervisor
 - Management and visualization of the alarms and events defined in the IoT event and alarm manager
- **IoT Supervisor:** The software component responsible to interact with the data sources to connect with the data streams and to create a unified interface hiding to the system configurator the low-level details of the connection. The IoT supervisor is directly connected to the following modules:
 - Data Injection interface: The IoT supervisor is externally exposed to allow the sensor the injection of the data streams to be processed by the VA4 NetApp.
 - Message Broker: Once a data sample is read and the data model has been unified, it is forwarded to the Message Broker (via MQTT) in order to make it available to the subscribers
 - Rest Controller: The configuration of the IoT Supervisor is implemented through the Rest Controller.
- **Message Broker:** The Message broker is the component that distributes the data collected from the sensors towards the components who needs to consume these streams, including data processors, data visualization tools, data storage tools etc. The implementation of this component is based on the RabbitMQ open-source software, a widely used tool supporting multiple messaging protocols
- **Datastore and Dashboard:** A scalable and flexible service, which is capable to store timeseries data, visualize it and retrieve it in an efficient way. In the context of the VA4 NetApp, it is used to store both

sensor data fetched by the IoT supervisor and alarms/event generated by the IoT event and alarm manager. It exposes the following interfaces:

- Data Injection Interface: a unified interface that exposes a backend-agnostic Injection API to the data producer
- Data Retrieval Interface: a unified interface that exposes a backend-agnostic Retrieval API to the data producer.
- Configuration Interface: a REST API to
 - Subscribe to a data stream
 - Remove a current data stream subscription
 - Edit the subscription parameter (retention policies, connection info etc.)
 - Interact with a set of storage plugins (configure remote mirror storages, derived timeseries, etc.)
- **IoT event & alarm Manager:** A software module able to generate alarms based on some configurable condition during the data stream analysis. The conditions could be based on a static or dynamic threshold or, instead, it is possible to define complex statement that depends by the value of one or more different sensors. Alarms and events could be redirected to an external MQTT broker and/or instantly sent by email or SMS. The IoT event and alarm manager exposes a REST interface to create/remove/edit conditions and to retrieve the current status of an alarm.

3.4.3 API and interfaces

The NetApp exposes the following interfaces (the OpenAPI specs will be reported in the next section):

- **Configuration REST interface:** Figure 34 explains the role of the Rest Controller in the VA4 architecture. It is able to cross-configure and control the status of the 4 core components of the NetApp. In particular, as described in its OpenAPI specs⁴², it exposes a REST endpoint composed by 3 main groups:
 - **/iot-supervisor endpoint:** it controls the status of the IoT supervisor. It allows to
 - Connect the IoT Supervisor to a specific fieldbus
 - Configure new virtual objects that continuously fetch new data samples from a physical sensor
 - Configure the VNF northbound interface to connect the IoT supervisor to the VA4 Message Broker
 - **/datastore endpoint:** it controls the status of the Datastore & Dashboard component. It allows to
 - Configure/edit/remove new data stream subscriptions to let the system able to store all the new samples in its backend
 - Enable and configure plugins and features offered by the system (configure remote mirror storages, derived timeseries, etc.)
 - **/alarm-manager endpoint:** it controls the status of the IoT event & alarm manager component. It allows to
 - Configure/edit/remove the conditions which are able to trigger events and alarms
 - Retrieve the status of an alarm already defined
- **Data Injection interface:** it is the southbound interface (SBI) directly connected to the data sources. The data produced from the sensors are directly injected to the IoT Supervisor, that should be pre-configured to be properly connected to the fieldbus.

⁴² https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_netapps/vital-5g-netapp-blueprints/-/blob/main/VA4/VA4.json

- **Data Retrieval REST Interface:** it consists in a unified interface to retrieve the stored timeseries from the Datastorage & Dashboard backend.

3.4.4 Deployment (IoT devices & 5G slices)

In Figure 35 we depict the two deployment scenarios currently targeted. The first one, described in D2.1 [1], considers a scenario in which this NetApp is directly attached to a 5G URLLC network slice to manage the IoT devices and sensors available in the field through an IoT gateway. In the second deployment scenario, VA4 uses the interfaces exposed by other NetApp (VA1 in the figure) to retrieve the IoT sensor data. Clearly in this second scenario, VA4 leverages the 5G connectivity through the 5G slice provisioned for the NetApp directly interacting with the IoT sensors (but it is not directly attached to the 5G slice). It is worth highlighting these scenarios are complementary and can be deployed in simultaneously for instance to control different sets of IoT devices.

Figure 35: VA4 Deployment Scenarios

3.4.5 Baseline software updates

The software supporting this NetApp is based on the NXWs Symphony software assets. The activities within VITAL-5G in this regard are as follows:

- **[Software Update]** Composition and Virtualization of NXW Symphony software assets: Different software assets of the Symphony suite have been integrated together using the functional block described in D2.1 [1] and virtualized inside Openstack based virtual machines.
- **[New Implementation]** Support for VA1 data injection interface: Development of the internal data model to support VA1 data injection through a message bus.

3.4.6 Software assets

3.4.6.1 Repositories / Images

VA4 is made available as a set of VM snapshots (qcow2 format) through the following FTP:

Server: mercurio.nextworks.it

Port: 9292

Files:

- **Rest Controller:** Vital5G_VA4_Rest_Controller.qcow2
- **IoT Supervisor:** Vital5G_VA4_Rest_Controller.qcow2
- **Message Broker:** Vital5G_VA4_Rest_Controller.qcow2
- **IoT alarm & event manager:** Vital5G_VA4_Rest_Controller.qcow2
- **Datastore & Dashboard:** Vital5G_VA4_Datastore_Dashboard.qcow2

3.5 VA5 Real time digital twin

3.5.1 Release features

The responsibility of this NetApp is to perform situational awareness. It makes use of all available radar sensor data to build a real-time model of the environment, namely an obstacle map of the surroundings of the vessel in the case of the Port of Antwerp. In later versions and other use cases, other input modalities can be used as well, depending on the availability of the sensor devices (radar, LiDAR).

VA5 is a vertical-agnostic NetApp because it is a generalized application that can be easily adopted for different services (e.g., to create a digital twin for autonomous vehicles, robots in warehouses). Furthermore, it is a publicly accessible NetApp, meaning everyone can re-use it to build a new vertical service. VA5 will be developed by IMEC, but it does rely on the sensors of SF for the Antwerp testbed. It will be deployed in the Antwerp testbed area.

3.5.2 Functional blocks

To create a digital twin of the environment, on-board sensor data is required. In later versions, sensor data is received directly from the vessel via a 5G interface. For this first release, recorded sensor data is used, so no real-time communication with the vessel is carried out. The preliminary software architecture is depicted in Figure 36. As can be seen, VA5 contains two main functional blocks:

- Radar data processing
- Occupancy grid map creation

Recorded raw radar data is used for this version of the NetApp. This data is processed to extract only the relevant information: binarization, dilation and filtering steps are carried out. After the data processing is completed, the image is formatted according to the needs of other NetApps to create an occupancy map and image metadata is generated. The resulting image and its metadata are then published via a Zero-MQ connection such that VS6 can use this map.

Figure 36: Software architecture of the first release of the VA5 NetApp.

3.5.3 API and interfaces

For this initial release, VA5 has the following interfaces:

- With the Assisted vessel navigation (VS6), which receives a map of the environment and the associated metadata.

Data exchanges with other NetApps are ensured by the ZeroMQ library, similarly to the other NetApps in UC1.

3.5.4 Deployment (IoT devices & 5G slices)

In Figure 37, we illustrate the overview of NetApps deployed within UC1, including the interaction between NetApps themselves, as well as their interaction with the vessel over 5G network. In case of VA5 in its later versions, the data collected from the vessel and its on-board sensors and camera is sent via eMBB slice, which is configured end-to-end from the UE (i.e., vessel) via 5G RAN and Core, to the NetApp platform where VA5 is deployed and running. The output of VA5, i.e., the dynamic occupancy grid map is further sent to VS6, thus, there is no downlink communication between VA5 and the vessel.

As VA5 is the first NetApp from UC1 that we present in the deliverable, we will refer to this figure in all other sections presenting the NetApps from UC1.

Figure 37: Graphical representation of NetApp deployment within UC1, including network slice utilization and NetApp interaction.

3.5.5 Baseline software updates

This section is not applicable to VA5 because no baseline software was previously specified.

3.5.6 Software assets

3.5.6.1 Repositories / Images

VA5 is made available as a Docker image on the Docker Hub repository⁴³: The access to Docker image (push and pull access) will be granted to collaborators by adding them to the repository Software structure (proprietary software of IMEC)

⁴³ <https://gitlab.ilabt.imec.be:4567/vital-5g/va5>

3.6 VA6 Data stream organization

The main role of VA6 is to aid in organizing the data streams that are coming from different sensors or from video streaming (as available from VS9 currently, but available from any other external NetApp or 3rd party) so that they are transmitted over a 5G network and permit the sensing system to be used by specific services and applications.

3.6.1 Release features

This release of VA6 currently has the following features implemented:

- Supports organization of data according to payload content
- Supports receiving data via Pub/Sub paradigms
- Supports custom processing functions (for organizing stream)

3.6.2 Functional blocks

Figure 38: Software architecture of the first release of the VA6 NetApp

VA6 receives data from other NetApps or 3rd parties that have data to be sent using the MQTT protocol. Its software architecture is illustrated in Figure 38

The main components of VA6 are:

1. An adaptor component from MQTT to InfluxDB

The adaptor is a Python script that subscribes a set of topics defined in the map configuration file and publishes the received data through the carbon interface of InfluxDB.

Two types of payloads are supported:

- number - n
- json - j

Each line in the configuration file contains two or three values:

- The first value represents the type of the expected payloads.
- The 2nd value represents the MQTT topic to be subscribed (wildcards are supported).
- The 3rd (optional) value represents the graphite key for the output.

When no 3rd parameter is specified, the Carbon key is obtained from the MQTT topic by adding “mqtt” in front and replacing slash (“/”) with (“.”).

The JSON format allows multiple values to be included in the same message. Also, using this format, we can specify the timestamp of the data, using the special designated key called “timestamp”.

Considering the payloads in Listing 2 and 3, we describe the examples in Table 11.

Table 11 Example of messages and their effect

MQTT message			InfluxDB entry			
#	Topic	Payload	Measurement	Field	Value	Timestamp
1	uc2/sat2	As in Listing 1.	mqtt.uc2.sat2	BAT	90	The 26th of November 2022, 3:54:20 am
				HUMID	40	
				TMP	25.3	
2	uc2/sat2	As in Listing 2.	mqtt.uc2.sat3	Alarm	0	The current timestamp of the adaptor.
				AQI	12	
				RSSI	2	

```
{
  "BAT": 90,
  "HUMID": 40,
  "TMP": "25.3",
  "PRJ": "Vital-5G",
  "timestamp": "2019-11-26T03:54:20+03:00",
  "status": "OK"
}
```

Listing 1. Payload for the first example in Table 11.

```
{
  "Alarm": 0,
  "AQI": 12,
  "RSSI": 2
}
```

Listing 2. Payload for the 2nd example in Table 11.

Please note that:

- string values are ignored if not convertible to int/float
- the payloads containing no timestamp are assumed to be for the current time (as presented by the RTC of the machine running the adaptor)

2. Time Series Database (OpenSource, InfluxDB⁴⁴)

⁴⁴ <https://docs.influxdata.com/influxdb/v1.8/>

We use InfluxDB 1.8. In InfluxDB 1.x, the data is organized in databases and measurements. For the current implementation of VA6 a single database is used. Each measurement presents the data in the associated fields. For being a time series database, when we select from a specific measurement, we get the data for the associated fields as well as a specific time.

3. Visualisation Engine (Grafana)

We use two types of dashboards for the visualisation engine:

- Graphical representations of time variation of measured parameters
- Overlay map displaying time series data

In order to represent time series data on an overlay map, we use The Worldmap Panel Plugin for Grafana. WorldMap is a tile map of the world that can be overlaid with circles representing data points from a query. It can be used with time series metrics, with geohash data from Elasticsearch or data in the Table format.

The Worldmap panel needs two sources of data:

- a location (latitude and longitude)
- data that has a link to a location

The data comes from a database query from InfluxDB.

3.6.3 API and interfaces

VA6 offers:

- An HTTP REST API interface used for querying the InfluxDB and supporting InfluxQL queries. The interface is the standard one offered by InfluxDB, and reference is available online⁴⁵
- A Grafana-based interface using the Worldmap Panel Plugin for Grafana⁴⁶

Figure 39: Visualization interface for VA6

⁴⁵ <https://docs.influxdata.com/influxdb/v1.8/tools/api/>

⁴⁶ <https://grafana.com/grafana/plugins/grafana-worldmap-panel/>

3.6.4 Deployment (IoT devices & 5G slices)

It uses the same sensors as in VS9 as data is received via VS9

3.6.5 Baseline software updates

VA6 represent an adaptation and modification of the existing Beia IoT cloud used in BEIA's own products and services. Changes and enhancements include:

- Modification of docker compose and configuration files for accommodating VA6 specific data coming from VITAL-5G testbed via VS9
- Better organization of InfluxDB topics
- Modification of MQTT to InfluxDB Adaptor

3.6.6 Software assets

3.6.6.1 Repositories / Images

The software components of VA6 produced in the project will be released as open source, and code is available in the project GitLab repository⁴⁷

3.6.6.2 Software structure (open source)

The install folder in the VA6 repository contains the docker files which allow to build and execute this module using Docker.

3.7 VS1 Indoor robot navigation & coordination with task planning

3.7.1 Release features

This marks the first full release of the VS1 NetApp. This NetApp along with the VA1 NetApp "Distribution sensor ingestion and automation" provides the necessary functionality to allow AGVs to perform autonomous transport operations within a warehouse.

The NetApp provides the following features:

- Logistics Lifecycle Management Service (Logistics LCM): API providing access to pending transportation jobs and warehouse products.
- AGV Task Allocation and Planning: Plan the AGV operations and send commands to the AGV through the MQTT broker provided by VA1.

⁴⁷ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_netapps/data-stream-organization

Figure 40: Sequence of messages exchanged between the AGV and the LCM component

3.7.2 Functional blocks

Figure 41: Components of VS1 NetApp and communication with VA1 and remote assets

The LLCM and Planning components described in the previous section utilize the services offered by the VA1 NetApp to communicate with remote devices such as Autonomous Guided Vehicles (AGVs). More details about the edge equipment are listed in the Deployment section below.

3.7.3 API and interfaces

The Logistics LCM component provides access to pending jobs and product placements to support the autonomous operation by the AGV. The main API endpoints are listed below:

orders	
GET	/api/v1/orders/active-orders Get active orders
POST	/api/v1/orders/create-orders Post a list of orders
GET	/api/v1/orders/next-order/{picker_id} Get next order to be picked
GET	/api/v1/orders/order-details/{order_id} Get details for a specific order
POST	/api/v1/orders/order-optimal-route/{order_id} Return the optimal route for a specific order based on the location provided
GET	/api/v1/orders/orders-generator/{status} Enable or disable auto order generator
POST	/api/v1/orders/update-order/{order_id} Update an order
products	
POST	/api/v1/products/create-products Post a new product. If the product exists it will be updated (A patch request must be added)
GET	/api/v1/products/product-info/{product_code} Get product details
GET	/api/v1/products/product-locations/{product_code} Get the locations a product is stored
GET	/api/v1/products/symbolic-location/{symbolic_location} Get symbolic location
POST	/api/v1/products/update-product/{product_code} Update a product

Figure 42: Logistics LCM API endpoints

3.7.4 Deployment

The VS1 NetApp provides functionality to the AGV deployed to the warehouse. The AGV has been connected to the 5G Network as depicted in Figure 41. Along with the AGV, warehouse device simulators have been deployed to assist in collecting KPIs (such as bandwidth and latency) since it is not feasible to have the AGV deployed in the operational environment of the warehouse 24/7. The details of the AGV are listed below:

- ClearPath Boxer 2.4(open-source firmware, ROS/ROS2 compatible).
- Capabilities: Move forward (speed up to 2m/s), move backwards, rotate, lift (~10cm).
- Sensors: Laser Scanner (LiDAR), RGBD camera, Inertial Measurement Unit, Motor Encoders.
- Custom cart designed for carrying EU pallets (120x80cm).

Along with the AGV, a telemetry station is prepared (but not yet deployed) based on Raspberry PI 4 with DHT22 Temp/Humidity sensors attached and a USB Camera.

3.7.5 Baseline software updates

The VS1 NetApp does not share any code or features with previous projects such as 5G-EVE. It is part of the WINGS Chariot platform developed by WINGS ICT Solutions and is covered by a proprietary license which allows usage within the scope of VITAL-5G, both by the VITAL-5G partners and 3rd-party experimenters.

3.8.2 Functional blocks

Figure 44: Components of VS2 NetApp and communication with VA1 and remote assets

The HMI assist and Computational offloading components described in the previous section utilize the services offered by the VA1 NetApp to communicate with remote devices such as Autonomous Guided Vehicles (AGVs). More details about the edge equipment are listed in the Deployment section below.

3.8.3 API and interfaces

The Video Controller service of the HMI assist component exposes the API endpoints depicted in the following figure. The computational offloading component retrieves video from the HMI assist component and textural messages through the MQTT broker, therefore it does not expose external interfaces or APIs.

Chariot Streaming Controller 0.1.0 OAS3

/api/v1/openapi.json

devices		^
POST	/devices/register	Registers a new device
POST	/devices/unregister/{device_id}	Removes a registered device
POST	/devices/connect	Sets connected status to a registered device.
POST	/devices/disconnect/{device_id}	Sets disconnected status to a registered device.
GET	/devices/status	Returns the current status of all registered devices.
GET	/devices/{device_id}/status	Returns the current status of a specific device.
POST	/devices/heartbeat	Devices keep sending post request to verify they are up
resources		∨
streaming		^
POST	/streaming/stream/{device_id}	Returns the streaming url of the requested device
POST	/streaming/stop-stream/{device_id}	Returns the streaming url of the requested device
servers		^
POST	/servers/register	Registers a new server
POST	/servers/unregister/{server_id}	Removes a registered server
POST	/servers/connect	Sets connected status to a registered server.
POST	/servers/disconnect/{server_id}	Sets disconnected status to a registered server.
GET	/servers/status	Returns the current status of all registered servers.
GET	/servers/{server_id}/status	Returns the current status of a specific server.
POST	/servers/heartbeat	Servers keep sending post request to verify they are up

Figure 45: HMI assist - Video Controller service endpoints

3.8.4 Deployment

The VS2 NetApp provides functionality to the AGV deployed to the warehouse. The AGV has been connected to the 5G Network as depicted in the previous diagram. The details of the AGV are listed below:

- ClearPath Boxer 2.4(open-source firmware, ROS/ROS2 compatible)
- Capabilities: Move forward (speed up to 2m/s), move backwards, rotate, lift (~10cm)
- Sensors: Laser Scanner (LiDAR), RGBD camera, Inertial Measurement Unit, Motor Encoders.
- Custom cart designed for carrying EU pallets (120x80cm)

Along with the AGV, a relative positioning system (Terabee™ “Follow-me”) is carried by a human operator to assist during the follow me operation to support the proximity-based collaboration with the AGV.

3.8.5 Baseline software updates

The VS2 NetApp does not share any code or features with previous projects such as 5G-EVE. It is part of the WINGS Chariot platform developed by WINGS ICT Solutions and is covered by a proprietary license which allows usage within the scope of VITAL-5G, both by the VITAL-5G partners and 3rd-party experimenters.

3.8.6 Software assets

3.8.6.1 Repositories / Images

The VS2 NetApp is offered as Virtual Machine image at <https://share.wings-ict-solutions.eu/vital5g/>. Software keys and guidance are provided to partners for onboarding the VM in the VITAL-5G platform. The VM has been deployed on the Athens testbed.

3.9 VS5 Remote vessel monitoring

3.9.1 Release features

A monitoring dashboard has been developed, tested, and integrated with other NetApps (VS8, VS7) that contains:

- 1) Camera view of the vessel (protected by password that can only be accessed by Seafar)
- 2) Real-time location of the vessel on an interactive 3D map
- 3) A view that shows the result of VS7 on the dashboard and allows for the user of the dashboard to interact with VS7

3.9.2 Functional blocks

The architecture for the first release of the NetApp can be found below. All visualized components are ready for this release.

Figure 46: VS5 architecture

3.9.3 API and interfaces

Communication between NetApps is done through a custom shared library developed by Imec based on ZeroMQ⁴⁸. To be more precise, the following NetApps are integrated:

- VS6
- VS7
- VS8
- VA5

Apart from the NetApps integration, integration with on board sensor has been achieved (On board camera).

3.9.4 Deployment (IoT devices & 5G slices)

VS5 is deployed on IMEC premises in a containerized manner. In Figure 37, we already presented the overview of NetApps deployed within UC1. In case of VS5, the uplink data is collected in the same way as for VA5, i.e., from the vessel and its on-board sensors and camera, and it is sent to the NetApp platform via eMBB slice. The output of VS5, i.e., the navigable waypoints and the optimized speed are displayed to the captain, and such this type of data is sent via downlink 5G communication leveraging on the URLLC slice.

3.9.5 Baseline software updates

VS5 is developed solely in the scope of VITAL-5G.

3.9.6 Software assets

3.9.6.1 Repositories / Images

A Docker image is available for IMEC to host on their premises.

3.10 VS6 Assisted Vessel Navigation

3.10.1 Release features

The Assisted⁴⁹ Vessel Navigation NetApp release will assist the captain of a vessel with navigation suggestions, consisting in global trajectory prediction. Real-time obstacle avoidance will be added in later versions. This NetApp will be deployed in the Antwerp testbed area.

Based on a given vessel position and parameters, on a desired destination and on knowledge of the navigation area, this first version of VS6 determines a path to the destination (global planning) and finds an optimized local path (local planning).

Global planning is achieved using Dijkstra's algorithm and assumes the availability of a complete binary map of the sailing area as data stored internally, prior to the execution of the NetApp (static map data).

Local planning is based on the generation of a set of candidate trajectories in the Frenet coordinate frame and their rating via a cost function. During local planning, vessel data and static map data are processed to produce waypoint suggestions, which are updated depending on goal information.

⁴⁸ <https://zguide.zeromq.org/docs/chapter5/>

⁴⁹ The name of the NetApp updated from Automated Vessel Navigation to Assisted Vessel Navigation to reflect on the NetApp operation in a correct way, thereby referring to the assistance that it provides for the vessel navigation.

3.10.2 Functional blocks

In Figure 47, we illustrate the preliminary software architecture of VS6 NetApp, i.e., the individual software blocks. We describe each of these components and the technologies that are selected for their realization as follows:

- The Map interlacing component performs a pre-processing step in order to generate the input for the planning algorithms. It combines the obstacle information received from the VS5 NetApp with stored information over the whole sailing route (start-to-goal static map, i.e. without obstacles).
- The Global path planner component receives the necessary vessel parameters (latitude, longitude, heading, speed) and the end goal information (latitude, longitude). In this version of the NetApp, these data are pre-recorded, due to operational constraints of the vessel. In the final version, the vessel parameters will be received in real-time from the VS8 NetApp and the goal information will be received from the VS5 NetApp. Together with the static map of the sailing area stored internally (image), it calculates positions (latitudes, longitudes) of intermediate goals up to the end goal. If called for the first time with a new end goal or new map data, the intermediate goal will be cached in the internal storage.

Figure 47: Software architecture of the first release of the VS6 NetApp

3.10.3 API and interfaces

For this initial release, VS6 has the following interfaces:

- With the Digital Twin (VA5) NetApp to receive pre-recorded vessel parameters and obstacle information.
- Data exchanges with the other NetApps ensured by the ZeroMQ library, similarly to the other NetApps in UC1.

Table 12 shows the current ZMQ topics subscribed, and payloads received by VS6.

Table 12 ZMQ topics subscribed and payloads received by VS6

#	Source	ZMQ topic	Payload
1	VA5	"allData"	{

			<pre> "dynamic_map": list of pixels, "vessel_orientation_on_map": "left", "meters_per_pixel": [1.0, 1.0] </pre>
2	VS5	"allData"	<pre> { "goalLatDegrees": 51.066562999999995, "goalLonDegrees": 3.715620000068759, "vesselHeadingDegrees": 270.0, "vesselLatDegrees": 51.067103, "vesselLonDegrees": 3.7191280000686646, "vesselSogKph": 0.0, "simulationReset": false } </pre>

Table 13 shows the future ZMQ topics published, and payloads sent by VS6.

Table 13 ZMQ topics published and payloads sent by VS6

#	Destination	ZMQ topic	Payload
1	VS5	"allData"	<pre> { "waypoints": [{ "lat": 51.06702715061826, "lon": 3.7187125533140475, "speed": 8.0 }, { "lat": 51.06698959015771, "lon": 3.718579780854476, "speed": 8.0 }, { "lat": 51.06695202969716, "lon": 3.718447008394904, "speed": 8.0 }, { "lat": 51.06691833674948, "lon": 3.7183127438748524, "speed": 8.0 }, { "lat": 51.06689077847739, "lon": 3.718176112638177, "speed": 8.0 }], "failure": false, "speed": 8.0 } </pre>

3.10.4 Deployment (IoT devices & 5G slices)

Same as in case of VS5, here we refer to Figure 37, where we already presented the overview of NetApps deployed within UC1. VS6 NetApp is currently deployed as a containerized NetApp on the NetApp platform on

imec premises within the 5G testbed, but as it does not interact directly with the vessel (only internal interaction with VA5), it does not directly leverage on any 5G slice.

3.10.5 Baseline software updates

This section is not applicable to VS6 because no baseline software was previously specified.

3.10.6 Software assets

3.10.6.1 Repositories / Images

VS6 is made available as a Docker image on the Docker Hub repository⁵⁰. The access to Docker image (push and pull access) will be granted to collaborators by adding them to the repository.

3.11 VS7 Navigation speed optimizer

The Navigation Speed Optimizer (NSO) uses APIs to retrieve the real-time data needed to calculate the optimal navigation speed for a vessel.

3.11.1 Release features

- VS7 is a back-end REST API. Client requests deliver information using JSON via HTTPS.
- It has been fully tested and integrated with VS8 to receive the geodata
- VS7 has been fully tested and integrated with VS5 to receive the planning data and provide the calculated optimal navigation speed in return
- All API traffic is encrypted with Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) certificates.
- For authentication, Open Authorization (OAuth) v2 is used.

3.11.2 Functional blocks

Figure 48: VS7 architecture

As seen in Figure 48, the data is collected from two sources: (i) client applications (i.e., other NetApps) and (ii) an inland navigation routing API. The client application, VS8, sends geodata of the vessel's current location and of the destination of the voyage to the NSO API. Based on these data, the inland navigation routing API, in this case the VisuRIS API, can retrieve the inland navigation route. Hence, it can calculate the distance to be sailed.

In addition to the geodata, the client application, VS5, also sends the time by which the vessel should be at its destination. This allows to calculate how much time remains for the vessel to sail to its destination. This data (i.e., the geodata, the navigation route and the time to arrive at the destination) is then used as input to the NSO algorithm. The optimal navigation speed is calculated as the division of the distance to the destination by the time remaining. The calculated optimal speed in kilometres per hour is then being converted to knots.

⁵⁰ <https://gitlab.ilabt.imec.be:4567/vital-5g/vs6>

The optimal navigation speed is then published in a topic on the queue to which the client application, VS5, can subscribe to retrieve the optimal navigation speed and integrate it into the vessel navigation assistance dashboard.

3.11.3 API and interfaces

The calculated optimal navigation speed can be retrieved by making a call to the REST API or by consulting the ZMQ queue. The NSO object contains the following data:

```
{
  startIsrs: string|null,
  endIsrs: string|null,
  eta: string|null,
  routeLength: number,
  optimalSpeedKmh: number,
  optimalSpeedKnots: number,
  lastUpdateTimestamp: number|null,
};
```

The destination can be retrieved by making a POST request to the `/destination` REST endpoint. The following message format is expected:

```
{
  "latitude": 51.254887,
  "longitude": 4.231544,
  "desiredTimeOfArrivalUtc": "2012-07-09T19:22:09.1440844Z"
}
```

3.11.4 Deployment (IoT devices & 5G slices)

As in case of the previous NetApps within UC1, we refer to Figure 37 for the overall overview of NetApps and their interaction on top of the virtualized infrastructure. Same as in case of VS6 NetApp, VS7 is currently deployed as a containerized NetApp on the NetApp platform on IMEC premises within the 5G testbed, but as it does not interact directly with the vessel (only internal interaction with VS8 and VS5), it does not directly leverage on any 5G slice.

3.11.5 Baseline software updates

The Navigation Speed Optimizer has not been part of any prior project.

3.11.6 Software assets

3.11.6.1 Repositories / Images

VS7 is available as a Docker image on Gitlab⁵¹.

3.11.6.2 Software structure (open source)

The repository of the Navigation speed optimizer service (VS7) contains a Node.js server which sits between the Onboard data collection and interfacing for vessel Tercofin II service (VS8) and the Remote Vessel Monitoring service (VS5), communicating with them via ZMQ and REST API.

⁵¹ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_netapps/vs7

3.12 VS8 On-board data collection & interfacing for vessel Tercofin II

The On-board data collection & interfacing for vessel Tercofin II, i.e., VS8 NetApp is the vertical-specific NetApp responsible for collection and processing of specific data coming from the on-board sensors of the Tercofin II vessel (i.e., the vessel used in UC1). The particular type of collected data from the Tercofin II is the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) data (i.e., speed, heading and location). Therefore, the Tercofin II relies on sensors on-boarded in the vessel as described in D1.1 [6]. This data is collected over the 5G network using a 5G eMBB 5G slice. For the purpose of interacting with other NetApps from UC1, and the 3rd party NetApps, the processed data is made available via a ZMQ pub/sub mechanism.

The design and development of VS8 was already finalized in the previous release, presented in the deliverable D2.2 [2]. The data collection mechanism presented in D2.2 [2] is considered as final, as it is sufficient for the purpose of collecting GNSS data from the vessel and sharing it with other NetApps in UC1. Thus, as there are no further software updates, all information related to VS8, i.e., its release features, functional blocks, APIs, interfaces, deployment, and software assets, can be found in D2.2 [2].

3.12.1 Release features

See D2.2 [2].

3.12.2 Functional blocks

See D2.2 [2].

3.12.3 API and interfaces

See D2.2 [2].

3.12.4 Deployment (IoT devices & 5G slices)

Concerning the deployment, in Figure 37 we illustrated the overview of UC1 NetApps interacting with each other and with the vessel. VS8 NetApp is currently deployed as a containerized NetApp within the BE 5G testbed. It dynamically collects real-time positioning data from the vessel, this data is being collected in the uplink direction, thereby leveraging on the eMBB type of slice. The output of VS8, i.e., the processed vessel positioning data is further sent to VS5, VS6, and VS7, thus, there is no downlink communication between VS8 and the vessel.

3.12.5 Baseline software updates

This software module is a newly developed NetApp for the purpose of interfacing with and collected data from the Tercofin II vessel. Its design and development (including interfaces with the other NetApps) are defined and executed within the confines of the VITAL-5G project.

3.12.6 Software assets

See D2.2.

3.13 VS9 On board data collection & interfacing for NAVROM vessel

This NetApp is responsible for collecting ship-related data from vessels in UC2 (i.e., AIS data, depth, engine, speed etc.), and it is made available for other VITAL-5G NetApps and 3rd party NetApps. This NetApp collects and data specific the NAVROM vessel(s) used in UC2.

3.13.1 Release features

The current release of VS9 supports the following data collected from vessel:

- Depth sensor data
- AIS data
- Engine data
- Air quality data
- Water quality data
- Video stream data

3.13.2 Functional blocks

Figure 49: VS9 architecture

Figure 49 illustrates the VS9 architecture. The main components of VS9 are:

1. Sensor data pre-processors (YOLO and AIS)
2. NodeRED based flow editor
3. MQTT Broker (EMQX⁵²)

In the following we briefly describe the main components:

AIS pre-processing

The automatic identification system (AIS) is an automatic tracking system that uses transceivers on ships and is used in vessel traffic monitoring. AIS information supplements marine radar (the primary method of collision avoidance for water transport). AIS integrates a standardized VHF transceiver with a GNSS (GPS, GLONASS,

⁵² <https://www.emqx.io/>

Beidou, etc.) receiver with other electronic navigation sensors (gyrocompass, rate of turn indicator, sea/river depth sensor, etc.).

An AIS transceiver sends the data in Table 14 every 2 to 10 seconds depending on a vessel's speed while underway, and every 3 minutes while a vessel is at anchor:

Table 14 Data sent by AIS transceiver every 2-10 seconds

Data	Measurement values/meaning
Vessel Maritime Mobile Service Identity (MMSI)	a unique nine-digit identification number.
Navigation status	E.g., "at anchor", "under way using engine(s)", "not under command", etc.
Rate of turn	right or left, from 0 to 720 degrees per minute
Speed over ground	0.1-knot (0.19 km/h) resolution from 0 to 102 knots (189 km/h)
Positional resolution	
Longitude	to 0.0001 arcminutes
Latitude	to 0.0001 arcminutes
Course over ground	relative to true north to 0.1°
True heading	0 to 359° (for example from a gyro compass)
True bearing at own position	0 to 359°
UTC seconds	The seconds field of the UTC time when these data were generated. A complete timestamp is not present.

In addition, the data in Table 15 are broadcast every 6 minutes:

Table 15 Data sent by AIS transceiver every 6 minutes

Data	Measurement values/meaning
IMO ship identification number:	a seven-digit number that remains unchanged upon transfer of the ship's registration to another country
Radio call sign:	international radio call sign, up to 7 characters, assigned to the vessel by its country of registry
Name	20 characters to represent the name of the vessel
Type of ship/cargo	

Dimensions of ship,	to nearest meter
Location of positioning system’s (e.g., GPS) antenna on board the vessel:	in meters aft of bow and meters port or starboard
Type of positioning system:	such as GPS, DGPS or LORAN-C.
Draught of ship:	0.1–25.5 meters
Destination:	max. 20 characters
ETA (estimated time of arrival) at destination:	UTC month/date hour:minute

Figure 50 shows the data capture implementation. As on the vessel AIS messages are received, they are converted to a serial interface standard and are sent to a Data Collection Device on board of the vessel. There they are decrypted; the various transmitted parameters being extracted. A selection of relevant parameters is made, and a data package is created (JSON format). The data package is sent through the 5G Infrastructure using the MQTT protocol to the BEIA MQTT broker. From there it can be forwarded to the rest of the VITAL-5G architecture. The information is also registered in an InfluxDB database and display using the Grafana platform.

Figure 50: AIS data capture implementation

YOLO for object detection

The YOLO algorithm has a high processing speed because it is a detection algorithm in a single stage (object classification is done without delimiting the region). The algorithm is based on a convolutional neural network, through which the contouring and classification of the object is performed. The workings of YOLOv5 with preparing and approval datasets and a custom-made YOLOv5 demonstrate for the classes appear in Figure 51

Figure 51: Object detection workflow YOLOv5

The classification-based YOLO algorithm is divided into two steps, the first step is to select the Region of Interest (ROI), and the second step is to select a distinct type of neural network that generally deals with the structure, similar grid, namely fully connected CNNs. CNNs are characterized by the fact that their main attribute is parameter sharing. In the case of CNN, weights are used in inputs, which refers to learning a set of weights for a particular location, which is an important feature that makes it reliable to detect objects.

Figure 52 shows the steps required to perform object detection using the YOLO algorithm. The camcorder records the video from which the images are taken and then scaled. The convolutions go through the frames of the image, and the outputs are filtered by non-max deletions, after which the detections are drawn on the results, and we obtain the desired file.

Figure 52: YOLO algorithm flowchart.

Node-RED flows

The main logic of VS9 is based on Node-RED. It provides a browser-based flow editor that makes it easy to wire together flows using the wide range of nodes in the palette. Flows can be then deployed to the runtime easily.

JavaScript functions can be created within the editor using a rich text editor. The necessary packages for the installation are Node.js, npm and Node-RED itself.

The Node-Red application connects with the testbed devices via the pre-processing blocks, gathers all the data from the sensors and publishes them in a specific JSON format to an MQTT. An example can be seen below

Figure 53: Node-RED flows from testbed sensors to MQTT

3.13.3 API and interfaces

VS9 offers a Pub/Sub mechanism supporting data that is published from the testbed sensors to any interested party (via MQTT subscriber clients)

Table 16 shows the currently sent MQTT topics and payloads sent.

Table 16 MQTT topics and payloads sent by VSg

#	MQTT topic	Payload
1	uc2/sensors/{shipName}/depth	{ "id": "GalatiPonton1", "value": "24" }
2	uc2/sensors/ais	{ "id": "GalatiPonton1", "aisString": "!AIVDM,1,1,,B,13ss?OwP00R0MCP IwfhdCOwp2W3h,0*0D" }
3	uc2/sensors/engine/#	{ "Rpm": "1304.88", "consumption": "90.45", "oil_press": "3.84", "engine_load": "45", "Air_filter": "12.75" }
4	uc2/video	{ "pre-process": "process", "inference": "inference", "NMS per image": "NMS" }
5	uc2/sensors/air/#	{ "id": "3981801", "id_wasp": "VITAL5G_Air", "id_secret": "42177063D9374202", "sensor": "BAT", "value": "94", "timestamp": "2022-10- 24T16:04:53+03:00" }
6	uc2/sensors/water/#	{ "id": "3981799", "id_wasp": "VITAL5G_Apa", "id_secret": "66641CE819623C42", "sensor": "WT", "value": "21.24", "timestamp": "2022-10- 24T16:04:34+03:00" }
7	uc2/sensors/sap/#	{ "id": "3981801", "id_wasp": "SAPBEIA", "id_secret": "42177063D9374202", "sensor": "HUM", "value": "44", "timestamp": "2022-10- 24T16:04:53+03:00" }
8	uc2/sensors/lidar/#	{ "id": "3981851", "id_wasp": "VITAL5G_Air", "id_secret": "42177063D9374202", "sensor": "distance_average", "value": "2410", }

		<pre> "timestamp": "2022-10- 24T16:04:53+03:00" } </pre>
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3.13.4 Deployment (IoT devices & 5G slices)

The VS9 is deployed on an eMBB network slice implementation.

The following IoT devices are used.

- **AIS transponder (SAAB R4 or Periskal PM-1)** – that provides data about the type of ship, the position of the ship, the speed of the ship, the angle made relative to the North direction, the type of voyage to be made, the estimated time to the end of that trip.
- **ACTISENSE DST 2 converter** – device to which the depth sensor is connected. Basically, it transmits pulses with a frequency of 200kHz (in the field of ultrasound) to the depth SENSOR (Airmar SS505). The ultrasonic wave generated by the sensor propagates to the bottom of the water.
- **PLC (Siemens IoT 20xx or Raspberry Pi)** – is a digital or analog signal adder and their transformation into digital signals converted into a protocol recognized by its peripherals (e.g. 5G router).
- **Depth sensor type Airmar SS505**

3.13.5 Baseline software updates

VS9 represent an adaptation and modification of the existing Beia IoT cloud used in Beia’s own products and services. Changes and enhancements include:

- Modification of docker compose and configuration files for accommodating UC2/VS9 specific data coming from VITAL-5G testbed
- NodeRED flow edited for specific UC2 testbed
- Custom JavaScript processing functions in the NodeRED flow
- Modification of receivers of NodeRED flow to accommodate data format sent from UC2 testbed

3.13.6 Software assets

3.13.6.1 Repositories / Images

The software components of VS9 produced in the project will be released as open source, and code is available in the project GitLab repository⁵³

3.13.6.2 Software structure (open source)

The install folder in the VS9 repository contains the docker files which allow to build and execute this module using Docker.

⁵³ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_netapps/data-collection-navrom

4 Updated workflows among software components

This section describes updated software workflows which refine or evolve the workflows described in D1.2 [3] or introduce new workflows not originally included.

4.1 Closed-control loops

In order to support closed-control loops at the VITAL-5G platform level, to enable the execution of automated control operations to react upon certain conditions or events to prevent or mitigate service disruptions in VITAL-5G we have defined or updated a set of workflows:

- **[Update]** Vertical Service onboarding: The vertical service onboarding workflow defined in D1.2 [3] has been updated to define a set of actions which could be executed at runtime to trigger network service scaling or network slice modification.
- **[Update]** Service Instantiation workflow: The service instantiation workflow defined in D1.2 [3] has been updated to include the configuration of the defined actions, and to illustrate how a service modification action is automatically triggered.
- **[New]** Network service scaling and Network Slice Modification workflows: Two new workflows have been designed to enable network service scaling and network slice modification

The VSB Service Onboarding modification is illustrated in Figure 54. As shown in the picture, the onboarding of the Vertical Service now allows the possibility of defining *RuntimeModifications* in the VSB. These modifications enable the establishment of automated actions which trigger different reaction types: (i) Slice modification (*SLICE_MODIFICATION*), to modify the slice profile parameters of the slice instance associated to the service instance; (ii) Network service scaling (*NS_SCALING*), to change scale up or down the network service instance associated. The target of the *RuntimeAction* determines the scale factor, which in the case of the network service scaling is the targeted deployment flavour, and in the case of the network slice modification determines the targeted slice profile characteristics. These actions can be triggered by two different types of triggers: (i) Threshold, which is used to trigger actions whenever a certain monitoring condition is met; (ii) Diagnostic event, to automatically trigger actions when certain AI-based diagnostic event occurs.

Figure 54: VSB Onboarding modification for closed-control loops support

The actions defined in the VSB are used during the service instantiation workflow depicted in Figure 55. As depicted in the picture, the Service LCM uses the *RuntimeModifications* to configure the internal module responsible for firing the events in order to subscribe to the correspondent topics on the monitoring platform. Once the triggering condition is met, the Service LCM automatically triggers the modification/scaling procedure.

Figure 55: Service instantiation and execution for closed-control loop support

The specific workflow to be followed upon triggering of a service modification request depends on the specific action (i.e., 5G slice modification or network service scaling), and are depicted in Figure 56. On the one hand, in the case of a network service scaling, the Service LCM can directly interact with the testbed NFVO to request the scaling of the network service instance to the specified scaling aspect. On the other hand, in the case of a 5G Slice modification, the Service LCM requests the new slice profile characteristics to the Multi-site 5G Slice inventory (which could trigger different actions based on the slicing capabilities of the different testbeds).

Figure 56: Network Service Scaling and 5G slice Modification workflows

4.2 Experiment Execution workflows

As mentioned in Section 2.2.2 in VITAL-5G we implement experiment executions through test cases associated with different NFVO Day2 actions. Figure 57 expands the definition of the experiment execution workflow defined in D1.2 [3] providing finer grained details for the “Execute test scripts on NetApps” step defined in the original workflow, in order to illustrate the how the execution of experiments is implemented. As depicted in the picture, the first step is to compute the actions and input parameters based on the information available in the TCB and ExpD. Based on this outcome, the Experiment LCM uses the NFVO LCM interface of the VITAL-5G testbed to trigger the actions which were defined.

Figure 57: Experiment Execution workflow expansion

In a similar manner, the “Clean NetApps Config” step described in [3] may use the TCB reset action to clean the experiment environment.

4.3 Slice inventory workflows

As the Slice inventory mainly interacts with the slice plugins on each of the 5G testbeds, Figure 58 provides a high-level overview of this interaction, showing the REST-based communication over the defined interfaces.

During the interaction between Slice inventory and 5G testbeds (Figure 58), the slice configuration details of pre-configured and newly configured 5G slices are collected and stored in the database. These configuration details are further used for determining which slice should be leveraged for the deployment of vertical services and NetApps.

Any entity within the VITAL-5G platform or external (e.g., 3rd party software component) can query the Slice inventory (Figure 59), select the network slices for vertical service deployment, require dynamic slice configuration (Figure 58), and send proper requests for retrieving the list of available slice instances and their configuration parameters (Figure 59). This entity could be e.g., Service LCM that is collecting the information about the available slices, which is further used for the NetApp and vertical service deployment.

In particular, this interaction between Slice inventory and Service LCM is shown in message 5 in Figure 58, as well as in message 12 in Figure 59. This interaction is invoked for allocating a slice for a specific vertical service, given the slice profile determined in the NetApp of Vertical Service Blueprint, or when a particular user needs to be dynamically attached to the selected 5G slice (belonging to one of three 5G testbeds). This dynamic slice creation or UE attachment are further requested by Slice inventory towards a 5G testbed, only, if possible, based on the input provided in the Testbed capabilities (D3.2). Such dynamic slice provisioning is shown in Figure 59 (message 12), when Service LCM requests from Slice inventory to select the most suitable slice for vertical service deployment. In that case, Slice inventory is first checking the profiles of existing slices, thereby comparing them against the slice profile characteristics demanded by Service LCM (e.g., certain levels of latency or required for vertical service deployment). If there is an existing slice that meets the requirements, Slice inventory responds to Service LCM, providing it with the information about the selected slice. However, if there is no slice that is suitable for such deployment, Slice inventory requests a corresponding 5G testbed to dynamically create a new slice. After new slice is created, Slice inventory stores the information about it, and responds to Service LCM, sharing the details of the newly created network slice.

Figure 58: Message sequence chart for the Slice inventory: Managing the availability of network slices in the 5G testbed.

Figure 59: Message sequence chart of the Slice Inventory: Interaction between external entities and the Slice inventory, and querying the list of slices/subscribers.

4.3.1 OSM Support of Day2 configurations

After an in-depth investigation of the support of Day2 actions in OSM, we discovered a bug which prevents execution of Day2 actions using input parameters in the version of OSM used in the testbeds (i.e. OSM release 10). A full report of the bug can be found here⁵⁴. As a workaround, the VITAL-5G Platform directly interacts with the JUJU controller of OSM to trigger the Day2 actions with the proper input parameters and values as depicted in Figure 60.

Figure 60: OSM 10 Interfaces and Workflow for Day2 execution

⁵⁴ https://osm.etsi.org/bugzilla/show_bug.cgi?id=2182

5 Conclusions

Deliverable D2.3 describes the first full drop of the BITAL-5G experimentation platform, including all accompanying tools and functionalities that set the stage for the VITAL-5G experimentation platform, open to both internal and external experimenters. The deliverable contributes to achieving one of VITAL-5G's milestones, *the first full version of the E2E VITAL-5G system*, making it available for full trials by experimenters.

The outputs of this deliverable serve towards the final version of the VITAL-5G platform and NetApps with full and relevant AI/ML tools, full versions of platform modules enabling the full versions of NetApps which would support the entire set of services for the use cases, fulfilling both envisioned service and business KPIs.

6 References

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Annex 1 – NetApp blueprints

For better use and representation of the NetApp blueprints, the JSON files of the blueprints of each NetApp are provided in the project public Gitlab.⁵⁵

⁵⁵ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_netapps/vital-5g-netapp-blueprints/-/tree/main